

1 **Fibrinolysis-unrelated functions of the plasminogen/plasmin**
2 **system: a gateway to successful parasitism?**

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10 **Abstract**

11 Parasites have evolved remarkable mechanisms to exploit host resources by subverting key
12 physiological pathways to facilitate their survival and transmission. A paradigmatic example of this
13 is the ability of some of these organisms to interact with the plasminogen (PLG)/plasmin system of
14 their definitive hosts, which facilitates parasite survival and dissemination through mammalian
15 tissues. The PLG/plasmin system has been historically referred to as the fibrinolytic system owing to
16 its major role in degrading fibrin clots, which depends on the conversion of the PLG zymogen into
17 the catalytically-active protease plasmin by the tissue-type and urokinase-type PLG activators (t-PA
18 and u-PA, respectively). Beyond this canonical role, the multiplicity of plasmin substrates and the
19 broad cellular expression of u-PA, the main extra-vascular PLG activator, engage the PLG/plasmin
20 system in a myriad of functions that are unrelated to fibrin clot removal, including brain function,
21 cell adhesion, wound healing, angiogenesis, inflammation/immunity, and cell migration.
22 Intriguingly, these processes are generally modified in parasitised hosts compared to healthy
23 individuals, suggesting that their manipulation may provide survival advantages to parasites. In the
24 present review, we explore the link between clinically-relevant endoparasites and the PLG/plasmin
25 system with a particular emphasis on how these organisms exploit its fibrinolysis-unrelated functions
26 to modulate host physiology and facilitate tissue invasion, immune evasion, and persistence within
27 the mammalian organism. Finally, we also discuss the involvement of this host–parasite interaction
28 in host pathogenesis, its potential for informing novel antiparasitic control strategies, and its broader
29 significance as a fundamental aspect of successful parasitism.

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34 **Keywords:** parasite, parasitism, plasminogen, plasmin, host–parasite interactions.

35 **1. Introduction**

36 The PLG/plasmin system, also known as the fibrinolytic system, plays a crucial role in maintaining
37 blood homeostasis by removing fibrin clots formed within the vasculature and in extravascular sites
38 where plasma proteins have extravasated, thereby preventing or limiting pathological processes
39 associated with their persistence or mislocalisation (**Figure 1**). Plasminogen (PLG), the zymogen of
40 the main fibrinolytic protease plasmin, is a glycoprotein of 791 amino acids and 92 kilodaltons that
41 is primarily produced in the liver by hepatocytes, although alternative organs, including the adrenal
42 glands, the kidneys, the brain, the spleen, the thymus, and the gut, have also been proposed as
43 secondary sources of PLG (Castellino and Ploplis, 2003). PLG is converted into plasmin upon
44 proteolytic cleavage by the serine proteases tissue-type and urokinase-type PLG activators (t-PA and
45 u-PA, respectively). This results in the generation of plasmin, a broad-spectrum, trypsin-like serine
46 protease composed of two polypeptide chains that are bound by two disulphide bridges (Lijnen,
47 2001a; Cesarman-Maus and Hajjar, 2005).

48 The t-PA is mainly produced and released by endothelial cells in response to different stimuli,
49 which preferentially confines the functions of t-PA within the vascular space, specifically in relation
50 to blood clot dissolution (Cesarman-Maus and Hajjar, 2005). In contrast, u-PA—also known as
51 urokinase—is produced by many different cell types including endothelial cells, leukocytes, renal
52 epithelial cells, some tumour cells, and intestinal epithelial cells (Gibson *et al.*, 1998; Cesarman-
53 Maus and Hajjar, 2005). The widespread cellular expression of u-PA explains why this protease is
54 the main driver of the fibrinolysis-unrelated functions of the PLG/plasmin system, although t-PA is
55 a key regulator of these functions in the central nervous system (CNS).

56 Over thirty years ago it was recognised that PLG not only interacts with fibrin but also with
57 cell surfaces, via a myriad of PLG receptors (PLG-Rs) that are broadly expressed by virtually all cell
58 types except for red blood cells (Miles *et al.*, 2021), allowing for the generation of plasmin beyond
59 the vascular compartment. The broad cellular expression of PLG-Rs, alongside the multiplicity of

60 plasmin substrates described in the literature (extensively reviewed in **Supplementary File 1**), imply
61 that the fibrinolytic system is involved in very diverse physiologic and pathologic processes that are
62 unrelated to fibrin degradation and blood clot removal. Notably, the fibrinolysis-unrelated functions
63 of the PLG/plasmin system are not solely mediated by the pleiotropic effects of plasmin or the
64 widespread expression of PLG-Rs, since additional fibrinolytic factors, including t-PA and u-PA, can
65 also modulate fibrinolysis-unrelated processes independently of plasmin generation and even of their
66 own proteolytic activity (Plouët *et al.*, 1997; Rogove *et al.*, 1999; Fredriksson *et al.*, 2004; Hu *et al.*,
67 2006; Su *et al.*, 2008).

68 Altogether, the versatility of the PLG/plasmin system make it an attractive tool for clinically
69 relevant pathogens, including parasites, which benefit from hijacking its fibrinolysis-unrelated
70 functions to enhance their survival and dissemination within the mammalian organism. This is clearly
71 exemplified by the ability of plasmin to degrade different proteins of the extracellular matrix (ECM),
72 which facilitates the subversion of tissue barriers by bacteria and their successful dissemination
73 within the organism (Bhattacharya *et al.*, 2012). The interaction between clinically-relevant
74 endoparasites and the PLG/plasmin system is a widespread phenomenon that mainly occurs through
75 the expression of PLG-Rs at the host–parasite interface, which causes a conformational change in the
76 PLG molecule that facilitates the conversion of bound PLG into plasmin by host-derived PLG
77 activators (González-Miguel *et al.*, 2016a; Diosdado *et al.*, 2022; Pala *et al.*, 2022). Although less
78 common, some parasites also express proteases that can directly cleave PLG into plasmin or activate
79 the precursors of PLG activators into their catalytically-active forms, thereby potentiating plasmin
80 generation (Keene *et al.*, 1986; Leontovyč *et al.*, 2018; Reiss *et al.*, 2021; Serrat *et al.*, 2025a).

81 Parasitic proteins that interact with the PLG/plasmin system are diverse and they are
82 expressed in different antigenic compartments and evolutionary stages of parasites (**Supp. File 2**),
83 suggesting that this interaction is important for the migration of larvae and asexual stages across host
84 tissues prior to their long-term establishment inside the mammalian organism as well as for the
85 survival of adults within their physiological definitive niche. Interestingly, the interaction between

86 the protozoan *Plasmodium falciparum* and the PLG/plasmin system has also been shown to be
87 essential for its development within the mosquito vector, providing interesting practical applications
88 for the control of this widespread parasite (Pala *et al.*, 2022). Fibrinolysis-unrelated functions of the
89 PLG/plasmin system that may positively impact parasite invasion and survival—thereby providing a
90 gateway to successful parasitism—include the regulation of brain function, cell adhesion and
91 migration, wound healing, angiogenesis, and inflammatory/immune responses. All these functions,
92 how they are modified during parasitic infections, and the potential involvement of the PLG/plasmin
93 system in their parasite-induced modulation are discussed in detail in the following sections.

94 **2. Fibrinolysis-unrelated functions of the PLG/plasmin system**

95 **2.1. The PLG/plasmin system in brain function**

96 The influence of the PLG/plasmin system in the CNS is mainly mediated by t-PA, as this is the
97 primary PLG activator expressed in the brain. Both plasmin and t-PA can modulate the activity of N-
98 methyl-D-aspartate receptors (Yuan *et al.*, 2009), either through direct cleavage or by interacting
99 with additional cofactors, which ultimately affects glutamatergic neurotransmission. By doing so, the
100 PLG/plasmin system is involved in physiological processes such as synaptic plasticity, learning and
101 behaviour, but also pathological conditions including seizures, dementia, multiple sclerosis, and
102 cerebral ischemia. In the brain, t-PA exhibits both neurotoxic and neuroprotective effects, primarily
103 depending on its pericellular concentration. Additionally, t-PA overexpression correlates with
104 increased blood-brain barrier (BBB) permeability during acute ischemic stroke, which might have
105 important therapeutic applications for this and other BBB-related disorders (Draxler and Medcalf,
106 2015).

107 In mice, increased BBB permeability caused by fibrinolytic hyperactivity depends on
108 plasmin-mediated generation of bradykinin (Marcos-Contreras *et al.*, 2016). Interestingly,
109 impairment of the BBB is one of the mechanisms proposed to underlie the neurological disorders

110 observed in some patients with liver infection by the trematode *Fasciola hepatica* (Mas-Coma *et al.*,
111 2014). These symptoms could be explained by the secretion of multiple PLG-Rs by *F. hepatica* adult
112 worms residing in the liver, which stimulate plasmin generation from bound PLG that potentially
113 acts on distant organs, including the brain (González-Miguel *et al.*, 2019). This notion is not far-
114 fetched considering that the ability of liver-dwelling *F. hepatica* to affect distant sites has been
115 demonstrated in experimentally infected rats (Saric *et al.*, 2010). In line with this, infection by the
116 protozoan *P. falciparum* causes increased BBB permeability through a bradykinin-dependent
117 mechanism (Silva *et al.*, 2019a), which could be partly accounted by the well-known ability of this
118 parasite to stimulate plasmin generation from host-derived PLG (Marcos-Contreras *et al.*, 2016;
119 Alves e Silva *et al.*, 2021). In addition to *P. falciparum*, other parasites, including *Toxoplasma gondii*
120 and *Taenia solium*, can cause a severe pathology in the CNS that is partly driven by parasite-induced
121 activation of tissue-remodelling matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) that compromise BBB integrity
122 (Mubarak *et al.*, 2025). Since plasmin activates MMP zymogens into their active forms (discussed in
123 the section “The role of the PLG/plasmin section in cell migration”), it is plausible that the interaction
124 between these parasites and the PLG/plasmin system (**Supp. File 2**) facilitates their migration
125 towards the CNS. Although a direct interaction between *T. gondii* and fibrinolytic factors has not yet
126 been experimentally demonstrated, the observation that pregnant women infected with this parasite
127 exhibit elevated plasma t-PA levels suggests a potential involvement of the PLG/plasmin system in
128 the pathophysiology of toxoplasmosis (Chou *et al.*, 2011). Additionally, increased expression of PLG
129 activators has been related to parasitic meningitis induced by the nematode *Angiostrongylus*
130 *cantonensis*, although additional research is needed to determine whether the host PLG/plasmin
131 system is actually involved in brain infection by this parasite (Tu and Lai, 2006; Lan and Lai, 2009;
132 Chen *et al.*, 2024).

133 **2.2. The PLG/plasmin system in cell adhesion**

134 The involvement of fibrinolytic factors in cell adhesion is primarily mediated by the physiological
135 receptor of u-PA (u-PAR) and the main fibrinolytic inhibitor, the PLG activator inhibitor 1 (PAI-1).
136 The u-PAR belongs to the lymphocyte antigen 6 (Ly6) superfamily of proteins and binds to the
137 somatomedin B (SMB) domain of vitronectin, promoting the adhesion of different cell types to the
138 ECM. In this case, the u-PA proteolytic activity is dispensable for cell adhesion, as u-PAR binding
139 to vitronectin is similarly achieved in the presence of u-PA truncated versions that only maintain the
140 receptor-binding domain (Kanase *et al.*, 1996; Chapman, 1997). Notwithstanding this, the binding of
141 u-PAR to vitronectin does increase in the presence of u-PA, partly through a conformational shift in
142 the u-PAR molecule upon u-PA binding (Ferraris and Sidenius, 2013). Another mechanism by which
143 u-PAR modulates cell adhesion is that involving integrins, which are transmembrane proteins that
144 modulate cell adhesion by linking the ECM with the cell cytoskeleton (Park *et al.*, 2020). Although
145 the interaction between u-PAR and integrins is a matter of debate (Simon *et al.*, 2000; Smith and
146 Marshall, 2010), it occurs either via direct binding to integrin extracellular domains or through the
147 formation of tripartite protein complexes that include integrins, u-PAR, and additional proteins such
148 as caveolin or maspin (serpin b5) (Chapman, 1997; Endsley *et al.*, 2011). Interestingly, members of
149 the u-PAR/Ly6 superfamily of proteins have been described in the trematodes *F. hepatica* (Shi *et al.*,
150 2014), *F. gigantica* (Davey *et al.*, 2022, 20), *Opisthorchis viverrini* (Mulvenna *et al.*, 2010) and
151 *Schistosoma mansoni* (Chalmers *et al.*, 2015), and proposed as potential vaccine candidates against
152 these parasites (Cardoso *et al.*, 2008; Chalmers *et al.*, 2015). Whether these proteins play a role in
153 the adhesion of these parasites to host tissues and whether this would depend on the concomitant
154 engagement of components of the PLG/plasmin system remains unexplored.

155 Cell adhesion is also regulated by PAI-1, which functions as a negative regulator of u-PAR-
156 mediated adhesion to vitronectin. This occurs either indirectly, via PAI-1-induced endocytosis of
157 membrane-bound u-PA/u-PAR complexes, or directly, by physically blocking the interaction
158 between vitronectin and u-PAR or that between vitronectin and integrins containing α_5 subunits

159 (Waltz *et al.*, 1997; Chapman, 1997). PAI-1 competes with u-PAR for vitronectin binding because
160 the binding site in the SMB domain of vitronectin for u-PAR is shared with PAI-1, so PAI-1 is
161 actually considered the molecular switch that regulates u-PAR-mediated cell adhesion and
162 detachment (Deng *et al.*, 1996; Ferraris and Sidenius, 2013). Moreover, in addition to u-PAR- and
163 PAI-1-mediated regulation of cell adhesion, plasmin itself cleaves vitronectin thereby removing the
164 binding sites for u-PAR (Waltz *et al.*, 1997), and different ECM components, including collagen type
165 IV and laminin, bind to both PLG and t-PA, enhancing t-PA-mediated PLG activation into plasmin
166 (Stack *et al.*, 1990, 1991; Moser *et al.*, 1993). Fibronectin is also capable of binding these fibrinolytic
167 factors (Moser *et al.*, 1993); however, unlike laminin and type IV collagen, intact fibronectin fails to
168 stimulate plasmin generation from bound PLG (Stack and Pizzo, 1993).

169 Remarkably, some bacteria express adhesion proteins that can concomitantly bind ECM
170 proteins and stimulate plasmin generation from bound PLG, which could represent an efficient
171 mechanism to target plasmin activity towards specific ECM substrates that would otherwise block
172 bacterial colonisation (Papasergi *et al.*, 2010). Whether parasites employ a similar strategy to
173 facilitate tissue migration is largely unknown. In this regard, newly excysted juveniles of the
174 trematode *F. hepatica* (FhNEJ) have been shown to express proteins at their surface that bind to
175 laminin, facilitating the adhesion of these parasites to the intestinal epithelium prior to migration
176 across the intestine (Serrat *et al.*, 2023b). Strikingly, some of the laminin-binding proteins expressed
177 by FhNEJ also bind to PLG and the precursor of u-PA (pro-u-PA), an interaction that results in
178 enhanced plasmin generation in the microenvironment surrounding the parasites and an increase in
179 their endogenous capacity to degrade laminin *in vitro* (Serrat *et al.*, 2023a; b, 2025a; O’Kelly *et al.*,
180 2024). Similarly, the protozoan *Trypanosoma cruzi* binds to laminin and fibronectin to adhere to host
181 tissues, which triggers proteomic changes in these parasites that facilitate their survival and
182 adaptation within the mammalian organism (Mattos *et al.*, 2012, 2019). Whether these ECM-binding
183 proteins would concomitantly bind PLG/plasmin to direct plasmin activity towards ECM components

184 that block parasite dissemination remains unknown, as the identities of fibrinolysis-interacting
185 proteins in *T. cruzi* have not been determined (Almeida *et al.*, 2004; Acosta *et al.*, 2016).

186 **2.3. The PLG/plasmin system in wound healing**

187 Wound healing refers to the repair of damaged tissues, a process that involves coagulation,
188 inflammation, cell proliferation, and ECM remodelling (Li *et al.*, 2003). Since plasmin is involved
189 in keratinocyte and inflammatory cell migration, activation of MMPs, the regulation of growth factor
190 activity and release, angiogenesis, and ECM dynamics, the PLG/plasmin system influences each and
191 every step of the wound healing process (Li *et al.*, 2003). In fact, impaired healing has been observed
192 in chronic wounds of diabetic patients containing decreased PLG accumulation, which ameliorate
193 upon repeated and local administration of this zymogen (Draxler and Medcalf, 2015). Similarly, a
194 reduced availability of PLG for plasmin generation in fluid derived from venous leg ulcers impairs
195 keratinocyte migration and re-epithelialisation of the damaged tissue (Hoffman *et al.*, 1998). The
196 importance of the PLG/plasmin system in wound healing is further supported by experiments carried
197 out in mice with defective or excessive expression of different fibrinolytic mediators, which show
198 impaired repair in different organs (extensively reviewed by Li *et al.* (Li *et al.*, 2003)). In line with
199 this, changes in the transcription levels of various fibrinolytic factors, namely t-PA, u-PA, u-PAR,
200 and PAI-1/2, have been observed in keratinocytes, fibroblasts, and endothelial cells during the earliest
201 stages of wound healing (Li *et al.*, 2003), further highlighting the importance of the PLG/plasmin
202 system in this process.

203 In relation to parasitic diseases, wound healing is a hallmark of helminth infections, which
204 elicit a T helper type 2 cell (Th₂) immune response aimed at limiting parasitic colonisation through
205 granuloma formation and intestinal ‘weep-and-sweep’ responses while simultaneously promoting
206 tissue repair to mitigate the damage caused by migrating parasites (Gause *et al.*, 2013). Proteins that
207 stimulate wound healing have been identified in different endoparasites and proposed as novel wound
208 healing therapeutics to promote tissue regeneration and treat chronic wounds, such as those present

209 in diabetic patients (Smout *et al.*, 2015; Lothstein *et al.*, 2024). Additionally, it has been demonstrated
210 that the nematode *Dirofilaria immitis* enhances wound healing in a PLG-dependent manner, as
211 revealed by increased migration of endothelial and smooth muscle cells upon co-incubation with *D.*
212 *immitis*-derived excreted/secreted products (ESPs) products and PLG (González-Miguel *et al.*,
213 2015b). In this model, the same effect was observed when replacing ESPs with the parasitic
214 recombinant antigens actin (DiACT), fructose-bisphosphate aldolase (DiFBAL), glyceraldehyde 3-
215 phosphate dehydrogenase (DiGAPDH), and galectin (DiGAL) (González-Miguel *et al.*, 2015a,
216 2016b), previously identified in this nematode as PLG-Rs expressed at the host–parasite interface
217 (González-Miguel *et al.*, 2013, 2015c).

218 **2.4. The PLG/plasmin system in angiogenesis**

219 Angiogenesis is the process of new blood vessel formation from pre-existing ones. The angiogenic
220 process begins with the overexpression and release of angiogenic factors by hypoxic, inflammatory,
221 or tumour cells. These factors include angiopoietin-2, fibroblast growth factor, and the vascular
222 endothelial growth factor (VEGF), the latter being the most potent mitogen for endothelial cells.
223 Upon binding of VEGF to the VEGF receptor 2 (VEGFR2), a downstream signalling pathway is
224 activated that induces endothelial cell proliferation and migration (Carmeliet and Jain, 2011; Ismail
225 *et al.*, 2021). The precise mechanisms by which t-PA, u-PA, u-PAR, plasmin and PAI-1/2 influence
226 angiogenesis are numerous and have been extensively reviewed elsewhere (Ismail *et al.*, 2021).
227 Briefly, u-PA promotes angiogenesis by stimulating intracellular signalling cascades in endothelial
228 and smooth muscle cells upon binding to its receptors u-PAR, the LDL receptor-related protein
229 receptor (LRP/ α 2MR), and to specific integrins. Since angiogenesis is a hallmark of cancer, the pro-
230 angiogenic effects of u-PA/u-PAR are particularly relevant in the context of tumour angiogenesis
231 and metastasis (Mazar *et al.*, 1999; Stepanova *et al.*, 2016). Additionally, u-PA can directly cleave
232 and activate VEGF (Plouët *et al.*, 1997), and nuclear u-PA has been shown to increase the expression

233 of cell surface VEGFR1 and VEGFR2 by interfering with the function of an inhibitor of VEGFR1/2
234 gene promoters (Stepanova *et al.*, 2016).

235 In contrast with u-PA, the ability of t-PA to activate angiogenesis is mainly plasmin-driven.
236 For instance, t-PA-mediated plasmin generation promotes the degradation of fibrin aggregates that
237 appear in blood vessels that have been permeabilised as a result of hypoxia (Pepper, 2001), thereby
238 inducing the formation of fibrin degradation products (FDPs) that stimulate endothelial cell
239 proliferation and migration *in vitro* (Bootle-Wilbraham *et al.*, 2001). Other than through the
240 formation of FDPs, plasmin fuels the angiogenic process by activating MMP precursors and
241 stimulating ECM remodelling, both essential for new vessel sprouting. In addition, ECM degradation
242 stimulates the release of ECM-sequestered growth factors that activate signalling pathways
243 responsible for endothelial cell proliferation and migration (Ismail *et al.*, 2021). Interestingly, PLG
244 itself can be cleaved by different proteases other than classical PLG activators, including neutrophil
245 and macrophage elastases as well as some members of the MMP family, to generate angiostatin-like
246 fragments (ALFs) with powerful anti-angiogenic effects that interfere with the proliferation and
247 migration of endothelial cells (Lijnen *et al.*, 1998; Lijnen, 2001b; Xu *et al.*, 2008; Brauer *et al.*, 2011;
248 Barrett *et al.*, 2017). In this regard, the protozoan parasite *P. falciparum* has been shown to hydrolyse
249 PLG and generate anti-angiogenic ALFs, a process that might contribute to immune evasion by this
250 parasite (Melo *et al.*, 2014).

251 In contrast to *P. falciparum*, helminth parasites belonging to different taxonomic groups
252 promote angiogenesis in the host, a phenomenon that is considered a prerequisite for successful
253 parasitism by allowing nutrient supply while facilitating the removal of potentially toxic waste
254 products from the tissue microenvironment surrounding the parasite (Dennis *et al.*, 2011). Different
255 molecules that directly stimulate angiogenesis in the absence of host-dependent mechanisms have
256 been described in several clinically-relevant endoparasites, including the trematode *O. viverrini* and
257 the cestodes *T. solium* and *Echinococcus multicularis* (Smout *et al.*, 2015; Carmen-Orozco *et al.*,
258 2019; Zhou *et al.*, 2024). Interestingly, the secretion of a pro-angiogenic factor by the liver fluke *O.*

259 *viverrini* has been linked to the ability of this parasite to stimulate cholangiocarcinoma (CCA)
260 development, which is strongly associated to infection by this parasite (Smout *et al.*, 2015). Although,
261 to our knowledge, the interaction between *O. viverrini* and the host fibrinolytic system has not been
262 described, the fact that its closely-related trematode *C. sinensis* interacts with PLG (Diosdado *et al.*,
263 2022) and is also considered a risk factor for CCA development (Feng and Cheng, 2017) suggests a
264 possible involvement of the PLG/plasmin system in liver fluke-stimulated angiogenesis that fosters
265 cancer development.

266 **2.5. The PLG/plasmin system in inflammatory/immune responses**

267 The involvement of the PLG/plasmin system in inflammatory and immune responses is demonstrated
268 by the fact that nearly all immune cells express at least one PLG-R, which facilitate plasmin
269 generation on their surface (Medcalf and Keragala, 2021). Additionally, multiple immune cells
270 produce and secrete t-PA, u-PA, PAI-1/2, and the thrombin activatable fibrinolysis inhibitor (TAFI),
271 further highlighting the connection between inflammation/immunity and the PLG/plasmin system,
272 which is nowadays recognised as an integral part of immune responses (Ploplis *et al.*, 1998; Das *et*
273 *al.*, 2014; Silva *et al.*, 2019b; Whyte, 2023). Mechanistically, the influence of the PLG/plasmin
274 system in inflammation/immunity can be categorised into: a) the ability of plasmin to influence the
275 complement system, fibrinolysis, and cell migration; and the regulation of inflammation-related
276 intracellular signalling (b) and of inflammation resolution and adaptive immune responses (c) by
277 different members of the PLG/plasmin system.

278 **2.5.1. Regulation of inflammation through the complement system, fibrinolysis, and cell** 279 **migration**

280 The complement system is composed by more than thirty soluble mediators, mainly serine protease
281 precursors, that are inactive until an infection or another trigger activates them. Upon stimulation,
282 the complement cascade stimulates leukocyte recruitment in the presence of invading pathogens and

283 orchestrates downstream adaptive immune responses (Ricklin *et al.*, 2010; Alberts *et al.*, 2022). The
284 interaction between the fibrinolytic and the complement systems is complex and somewhat
285 controversial (Draxler *et al.*, 2017), with some studies reporting plasmin(ogen) as a complement
286 activator and others, as a complement inhibitor. However, given the intricate network of
287 interconnected pathways that constitute the complement system, it is expected that plasmin(ogen)
288 exerts both stimulatory and inhibitory effects depending on the specific arm of the complement
289 cascade being regulated (Foley, 2017).

290 In general, plasmin activates the complement pathway downstream of C3, for instance, by
291 cleaving C5 and generating C5-derived fragments that are chemotactic to neutrophils. However,
292 plasmin can also have potent complement inhibitory effects by degrading C3b, which lies upstream
293 in the complement cascade and plays a major role in amplifying complement-mediated responses
294 (Draxler *et al.*, 2017; Foley, 2017). This function is exploited by bacteria through the recruitment of
295 PLG at their surface and its subsequent conversion into plasmin in order to evade complement-
296 mediated defences, which are particularly proficient against bacterial infections (Foley, 2017). In line
297 with this, different parasites have also evolved mechanisms to evade the complement system by
298 binding or degrading its components, thereby reducing the pool of molecules available for the
299 assembly of complement effectors (Pereira-Filho *et al.*, 2023; Heggi *et al.*, 2024). For instance, *P.*
300 *falciparum* was shown to evade complement-mediated immune attacks through the stimulation of
301 plasmin generation from host-derived PLG, leading to the degradation of the complement molecule
302 C3b (Reiss *et al.*, 2021; Ernest *et al.*, 2023). C3b is considered a central regulator of the complement
303 cascade by interacting with additional complement molecules to form the C5 convertase, which
304 cleaves C5 into C5a and C5b, the latter being a central component of the membrane attack complex
305 (MAC)—the terminal effector of the complement system that is essential for pathogen clearance.
306 The trematode *F. hepatica* has also evolved mechanisms to evade complement-mediated immunity
307 (De Marco Verissimo *et al.*, 2022), but whether this is mediated by the well-established capacity of
308 this parasite to interact with the PLG/plasmin system (González-Miguel *et al.*, 2019; Serrat *et al.*,

309 2023a, 2025a; O’Kelly *et al.*, 2024) is largely unknown. In this regard, epithelial cells of the mouse
310 small intestine, when co-stimulated with both FhNEJ and PLG—a combination that leads to
311 increased plasmin generation in the pericellular space—downregulate the expression of the
312 complement effector C7, a central component of the MAC (Serrat *et al.*, 2025b).

313 In addition to regulating the complement system, plasmin also modulates inflammatory
314 responses through its fibrinolytic functions. Fibrin matrices are provisionally deposited at virtually
315 any site of overt tissue damage induced by invading pathogens or inflammatory triggers, thereby
316 representing a scaffold for leukocyte recruitment and migration. This occurs via the interaction
317 between leukocyte integrin $\alpha_M\beta_2$ and fibrin(ogen), which facilitates the adhesion of these cells to sites
318 of injury (Flick *et al.*, 2004; Baker and Strickland, 2020). In this scenario, plasmin would have an
319 anti-inflammatory effect by removing fibrin. However, leukocyte mobilisation to infected sites is
320 also facilitated by the ability of plasmin to degrade ECM components and activate MMP precursors,
321 two processes that are crucial for the migration of inflammatory cells (discussed in the following
322 section). Independently of inflammation, the recruitment of plasmin at the parasite surface, or its
323 generation from host-derived surface-bound PLG, may also serve as a mechanism to degrade fibrin
324 clots that would otherwise cause the immobilisation and reduced survival of parasites residing within
325 the vascular system, such as the helminths *S. mansoni* and *D. immitis* (González-Miguel *et al.*,
326 2016a).

327 **2.5.2. Regulation of inflammation-related intracellular signalling**

328 The PLG/plasmin system plays a pivotal role in regulating intracellular signalling pathways that drive
329 inflammatory responses, a function that is predominantly mediated by plasmin-mediated generation
330 of signal transducers and by u-PA/u-PAR. Fibrin degradation by plasmin generates different FDPs,
331 including fragments D and E, D-dimer, $B_{\beta 1-42}$, $B_{\beta 15-42}$ and α chain (alphastatin) (**Supp. File 1**), that
332 stimulate the production of both pro- and anti-inflammatory mediators by modulating mitogen-
333 activated protein kinase, protein kinase C, and nuclear factor κB signalling (Jennewein *et al.*, 2011).

334 In addition, in macrophages, plasmin-mediated cleavage of the PLG-R annexin A2 generates an
335 amino-terminal peptide that serves as a ligand for adjacent transmembrane receptors, thereby
336 triggering intracellular signalling cascades that result in inflammatory cytokine/chemokine
337 production and an increase in bacterial phagocytosis (Swisher *et al.*, 2007).

338 Regarding the u-PAR, its contribution to intra-vascular fibrinolysis is minimal, as shown by
339 an absence of thrombotic disorders or spontaneous fibrin deposition in u-PAR knock-out (KO) mice
340 (Dewerchin *et al.*, 1996). Since these mice do present significant alterations in inflammatory
341 responses (Gyetko *et al.*, 2000; Cheng *et al.*, 2022), the activation of inflammation-related
342 intracellular signalling, rather than PLG activation, is considered the major biological function of u-
343 PAR, which is considered a central regulator of inflammation and immunity (Hamada *et al.*, 2024).
344 The u-PAR regulates signalling upstream of tyrosine-kinase receptors (e.g., the epidermal growth
345 factor receptor), G protein-coupled receptors (e.g., formyl peptide receptors); and integrins, all of
346 them being important regulators of inflammatory and immune responses (Pastore *et al.*, 2008;
347 Ferraris and Sidenius, 2013; Weiß and Kretschmer, 2018). Despite controversy (Simon *et al.*, 2000;
348 Smith and Marshall, 2010), it is generally accepted that u-PAR interacts with integrins containing β_1
349 and β_3 subunits and with integrin $\alpha_M\beta_2$ (also known as MAC-1, CD11b, CD18 or CR3) on the cell
350 surface (Smith and Marshall, 2010; Ferraris and Sidenius, 2013), which mediate the relay of u-PAR-
351 dependent signals to the intracellular space. Integrins are involved in innate/inflammatory and
352 adaptive immune responses by regulating the rolling, adhesion, crawling, and transendothelial
353 migration of leukocytes, as well as antigen presentation to resting T cells (Park *et al.*, 2020).

354 Regarding the potential involvement of the PLG/plasmin system in parasitic infections
355 through the regulation of intracellular signalling, evidence is still scarce. However, previous studies
356 reported an increase in u-PAR expression in brain specimens of patients who died from cerebral
357 malaria, potentially linking the immunological dysfunction and subsequent BBB disintegration that
358 is commonly observed in these patients with altered inflammation-related and u-PAR-dependent
359 intracellular signalling (Fauser *et al.*, 2000). Additionally, given that u-PAR is a member of the Ly6

360 superfamily of proteins and that such proteins have been identified in different parasite species
361 (Mulvenna *et al.*, 2010; Shi *et al.*, 2014; Chalmers *et al.*, 2015; Davey *et al.*, 2022), investigating
362 whether parasite-derived Ly6 proteins regulate intracellular signalling routes in inflammatory cells
363 that regulate their behaviour similarly to u-PAR would provide valuable insights into the plethora of
364 mechanisms employed by parasitic organisms to modulate host immune responses.

365 **2.5.3. Regulation of inflammation resolution and adaptive immunity**

366 In addition to promoting inflammatory responses, the PLG/plasmin system has recently been
367 attributed significant roles in resolving inflammation (Perucci *et al.*, 2023), a pathway that could
368 benefit parasites by enabling them to remain unnoticed. Functions of the PLG/plasmin system in
369 inflammation resolution include fibrin removal from injured sites and the stimulation of anti-
370 inflammatory cytokine release, neutrophil apoptosis, efferocytosis (phagocytosis of apoptotic
371 neutrophils by macrophages), and macrophage polarisation towards an anti-inflammatory or pro-
372 resolution M2 phenotype (Vago *et al.*, 2019; Perucci *et al.*, 2023). Interestingly, the induction of an
373 alternatively-activated M2 phenotype in macrophages is a hallmark in many helminth infections and
374 represents a potent mechanism of host immune suppression (Maizels and McSorley, 2016), raising
375 the question of whether this process is also facilitated by parasite-induced plasmin generation.

376 Regarding adaptive immunity, the expression of different PLG-Rs by T cells, which also
377 overexpress t-PA upon activation, allows for plasmin generation on the cell surface and the
378 subsequent plasmin-stimulated cleavage of certain chemokines, establishing a gradient that increases
379 dendritic cell recruitment to the infected site (Loef *et al.*, 2022)—a crucial step in initiating antibody-
380 mediated adaptive immune responses. Although no studies have directly demonstrated that parasites
381 exploit the PLG/plasmin system to regulate such responses, the ability of plasmin to degrade
382 immunoglobulins (Chuba, 1994; Crane *et al.*, 2009) provides strong grounds to consider that
383 hijacking its proteolytic activity might represent a mechanism employed by parasites to regulate
384 adaptive immune responses. In line with this, plasmin has been suggested to locally promote the

385 skewing of adaptive immunity toward a Th2-dominated profile, which is typically induced during
386 helminth infections (Okada *et al.*, 2013; Gause *et al.*, 2013; Draxler *et al.*, 2017). Altogether, the
387 widespread influence of the PLG/plasmin system on immunity (**Figure 2**) strongly supports its co-
388 option by parasites as a key strategy for modulating host immune responses and ensuring their long-
389 term establishment within the mammalian organism (Ayón-Núñez *et al.*, 2018). However, direct
390 experimental evidence proving this point remains limited to the aforementioned studies
391 demonstrating parasite-mediated regulation of the complement cascade in a plasmin-dependent
392 manner.

393 **2.6. The role of the PLG/plasmin system in cell migration**

394 A key similarity between wound healing, angiogenesis, and the immune/inflammatory response is
395 their dependence on cell migration. Therefore, in these contexts, the contribution of the PLG/plasmin
396 system is also reflected in the ability of plasmin to facilitate the migration of different cell types,
397 including endothelial cells and leukocytes. In this regard, u-PAR contributes to inflammation by
398 localising plasmin activity at the leading edge of migrating leukocytes (Smith and Marshall, 2010;
399 Ferraris and Sidenius, 2013). Migration across host tissues is also a hallmark in many parasite
400 infections, including those by metazoan parasites, which is somewhat unexpected considering that it
401 incurs a high energy cost. However, gastrointestinal (GI) nematodes that migrate through different
402 organs are generally larger in size than their closest relatives that develop exclusively within the GI
403 tract. Since body size correlates with fecundity in GI nematodes, parasite migration is considered a
404 selective advantage that has been maintained across evolution to maximise parasite transmission
405 (Read and Skorpung, 1995).

406 Provided that the mechanisms underlying parasite migration closely resemble those involved
407 in leukocyte trafficking (Yeh *et al.*, 2024), it is plausible that the PLG/plasmin system also plays a
408 role in the migration of parasites across host tissues. In general, plasmin stimulates cell migration
409 through the direct degradation of ECM components, including laminin, fibronectin, and

410 proteoglycans, as well as by cleaving and activating MMP zymogens (**Supp. File 1**). This association
411 has been observed in the context of dirofilariosis using an *in vitro* cell model, where extracts and
412 proteins from the *D. immitis* host–parasite interface were able to enhance the degradation of the major
413 ECM protein, collagen type I, in the presence of host PLG (González-Miguel *et al.*, 2015a; b, 2016b).
414 Similarly, the ability of *F. hepatica* juveniles to degrade laminin *in vitro* is enhanced in the presence
415 of PLG and host-derived PLG activators (Serrat *et al.*, 2023b). In addition, since cellular migration
416 is highly dependent on an interplay between forces of adhesion and detachment (Chapman, 1997),
417 the u-PAR/PAI-1/plasmin-regulated mechanisms of cell adhesion described in the corresponding
418 preceding section should also be regarded as important modulators of cell migration.

419 The MMPs are zinc dependent endopeptidases that cleave multiple substrates, including
420 intercellular proteins (e.g., epithelial junction proteins) and virtually all structural ECM proteins
421 (Cauwe *et al.*, 2007; Pompili *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, plasmin-mediated cleavage and activation of
422 MMP precursors represents a potent stimulator of ECM degradation and cell migration both in
423 physiological and pathological contexts (Festuccia *et al.*, 1999; Legrand *et al.*, 2001; Gong *et al.*,
424 2008; Ishihara *et al.*, 2012). Plasmin activates the precursor zymogens of MMP-1, -2, -3, -9, -10, -12
425 and -13, either via direct cleavage or by activating other MMPs that, in turn, cleave and activate
426 another MMP precursor (Suzuki *et al.*, 1990; Baramova *et al.*, 1997; Carmeliet *et al.*, 1997; Ramos-
427 DeSimone *et al.*, 1999; Hahn-Dantona *et al.*, 1999; Saunders *et al.*, 2005; Orbe *et al.*, 2009; Sonoki
428 *et al.*, 2018). The MMP-1 zymogen is activated by plasmin through the generation of an intermediate
429 form with minimal catalytic activity that is more readily activated by MMP-3 than the intact pro-
430 MMP-1 molecule (Suzuki *et al.*, 1990). Similarly, MMP-2 is activated in a two-step process that
431 involves the generation of an inactive MMP-2 intermediate by membrane-type (MT) 1-MMP that is
432 subsequently converted into fully active MMP-2 by plasmin cleavage (Baramova *et al.*, 1997).
433 Regarding pro-MMP-9 activation, the use of cell-free or MMP-3-deficient systems has demonstrated
434 that plasmin does not directly cleave and activate pro-MMP-9; rather, MMP-9 generation depends
435 on plasmin-mediated cleavage and activation of pro-MMP-3 into active MMP-3, which is a potent

436 activator of the MMP-9 zymogen (Okada *et al.*, 1992; Ramos-DeSimone *et al.*, 1999; Hahn-Dantona
437 *et al.*, 1999). Although a study by Carmeliet *et al.* (Carmeliet *et al.*, 1997) concluded that there is
438 direct activation of pro-MMP-9 by plasmin, their results could be explained by the presence of pro-
439 MMP-3 in the conditioned cell media that the authors employed for their MMP-9 activation assays.

440 Along with the creation of migratory paths through the degradation of ECM structural
441 proteins, MMPs also stimulate cell migration by cleaving and processing various cytokines and
442 chemotactic molecules (Rodríguez *et al.*, 2010), a process that is particularly relevant during
443 inflammatory cell migration; and by directly cleaving and degrading intercellular junction proteins
444 that maintain epithelial barrier function, including cadherins, occludins, and claudins (Cauwe *et al.*,
445 2007; Al-Dasooqi *et al.*, 2014). Notably, the degradation of tight junction proteins mediated by
446 MMP-9 has recently been implicated in the pathogenesis of Dengue virus infection (Pan *et al.*, 2021)
447 and partially explains the loss of epithelial barrier integrity that is associated with intestinal
448 inflammatory disorders (Magali de Bruyn and Opdenakker, 2016). Although some parasites express
449 MMP-like enzymes that aid in tissue invasion (McGwire *et al.*, 2003; Williamson *et al.*, 2006),
450 whether the interaction between tissue-migrating parasites and the PLG/plasmin system represents a
451 strategy to hijack the host-derived MMP machinery to sustain tissue migration remains understudied.
452 To the best of our knowledge, this function has so far only been reported in *D. immitis*, whose ESPs
453 and recombinant antigens DiACT, DiFBAL, DiGAPDH, and DiGAL stimulate MMP-2 (and in some
454 cases, MMP-9) activity in the presence of host PLG in an *in vitro* model (González-Miguel *et al.*,
455 2015a; b, 2016b). In addition to plasmin-mediated MMP activation, some studies show that u-PA is
456 capable of directly cleaving and activating certain MMP precursors irrespective of plasmin
457 generation, including pro-MMP-2 (Shin *et al.*, 2010) and pro-MMP-9 (Keski-Oja *et al.*, 1992).
458 Interestingly, a protein extract derived from FhNEJ has been recently shown to cleave the precursor
459 zymogen of u-PA (pro-u-PA) into its catalytically active form (Serrat *et al.*, 2025a), which could
460 facilitate parasite migration through host tissues by increasing the pool of enzymes that are available
461 to activate host-derived MMPs.

462 In addition to cleavage of MMP zymogens into their active forms, another layer of regulation
463 of the MMP system by fibrinolytic components, such as t-PA and PAI-1, is the modulation of the
464 expression levels of MMP-3, -9, and -13 (Hu *et al.*, 2006; Pagliara *et al.*, 2014; Moritake *et al.*, 2019;
465 Saleem *et al.*, 2021). Changes in MMP expression can also involve PLG binding, as shown by
466 increased MMP-1 synthesis by monocytic cells upon plasmin-dependent signalling through the PLG-
467 R annexin A2 (Zhang *et al.*, 2007). In line with this, a recent study has shown that *F. hepatica*
468 juveniles stimulate the secretion of different MMPs by intestinal epithelial cells derived from the
469 mouse intestine, although this effect appeared to be PLG-independent (Serrat *et al.*, 2025b).

470 Adding further complexity, the interaction between the PLG/plasmin and MMP systems is
471 reciprocal, with MMPs also modulating the functions of different fibrinolytic factors. Specifically,
472 MMP-3, -12, -19, MT6-MMP, and a bacterial-derived MMP cleave and modulate the activities of u-
473 PAR (Koolwijk *et al.*, 2001; Andolfo *et al.*, 2002; Leduc *et al.*, 2007); and PLG degradation by
474 MMP-3 inhibits the migration of a human breast cancer cell line (Farina *et al.*, 2002). As mentioned
475 in the corresponding preceding section, certain MMPs, including MMP-3, -7, -9, and -12 cleave PLG
476 to generate ALFs with potent anti-angiogenic effects, which represents a mechanism to shut down
477 fibrinolysis by reducing the pool of PLG that is available for plasmin generation (Lijnen, 2001b).
478 Additionally, MMP-10 exhibits a profibrinolytic activity by degrading TAFI, a key modulator of
479 haemostasis that inhibits fibrinolysis by removing C-terminal lysines in fibrin that are required for
480 PLG binding (Orbe *et al.*, 2011). Moreover, cleavage of the PLG-R annexin A2 by MMP-7 enhances
481 binding of t-PA to a human colon cancer cell line, potentially enhancing the metastatic capacity of
482 these cells (Tsunezumi *et al.*, 2008). Finally, MMP-like proteases present in snake venoms cleave
483 and activate pro-u-PA, which may contribute to the lethal haemorrhages associated with snake
484 envenomation (Sugiki *et al.*, 1998). This observation provides an intriguing clue into the possible
485 identity of the proteases expressed by *F. hepatica* juveniles that are capable of activating pro-u-PA
486 (Serrat *et al.*, 2025a), especially considering that metalloproteases have been described in ESPs of
487 these parasites (Di Maggio *et al.*, 2016).

488 **3. Concluding remarks**

489 Given the pleiotropic roles of the PLG/plasmin system outlined in this review, it stands to reason that
490 co-opting its functions may represent a crucial mechanism exploited by parasites to circumvent host-
491 derived immune defences and migrate more efficiently across mammalian tissues (**Figure 3**). The
492 interaction between parasites and the PLG/plasmin system is not only observed in parasites belonging
493 to different taxa but also in bacteria and fungi (Bhattacharya *et al.*, 2012; Chen *et al.*, 2020), thereby
494 representing a paradigmatic example of evolutionary convergence wherein phylogenetically
495 unrelated species develop analogous strategies to fulfil a specific biological purpose. Additionally,
496 the interaction between parasites and the PLG/plasmin system is highly redundant, as it involves the
497 expression of multiple PLG-Rs by the same parasitic organism (**Supp. File 2** and (Diosdado *et al.*,
498 2022)). Since biochemical redundancy allows for the maintenance of essential biological functions
499 by providing back-up mechanisms that can operate when a specific effector protein is lost (Nowak *et*
500 *al.*, 1997), this observation reveals the importance of hijacking the host PLG/plasmin system for
501 parasites. Moreover, PLG-Rs are often intracellular proteins with canonical housekeeping functions
502 unrelated to immune regulation or parasite migration, which argues in favour of a moonlighting
503 potential of most parasitic PLG-Rs (González-Miguel *et al.*, 2016a). The use of housekeeping core
504 metabolic enzymes or cytoskeletal/cell cycle proteins for invasion and adhesion confers an
505 evolutionary advantage to parasites by minimising immune recognition, as these proteins are highly
506 conserved across species, including mammals, and targeting them could lead to undesired self-
507 recognition.

508 Since parasitic proteins that interact with the host PLG/plasmin system are located at the
509 interface between both organisms, one of the most compelling applications of parasitic proteins that
510 interact with this system is their potential use in vaccine development. However, as previously noted,
511 the interaction between parasites and the PLG/plasmin system is highly redundant and commonly
512 exerted by metabolic enzymes, including enolase, GAPDH, and FBAL, with significantly conserved

513 sequences across various species (Ghosh and Jacobs-Lorena, 2011), posing serious challenges to
514 their use as vaccine targets (Figueiredo *et al.*, 2015; Diosdado *et al.*, 2022). That said, targeting a
515 single PLG-binding protein in *Candida albicans* significantly reduced mortality rates in infected
516 mice (Chen *et al.*, 2020) despite the interaction between this pathogen and the PLG/plasmin system
517 being redundant (Crowe *et al.*, 2003), and blocking species-specific epitopes of *Plasmodium* GAPDH
518 reduced sporozoite infectivity without undesired host recognition (Cha *et al.*, 2018). In line with this,
519 the high species-specificity of the interaction between u-PA and its physiological receptor, u-PAR
520 (Lin *et al.*, 2010), underscores the potential of blocking this interaction as a selective target for
521 parasites that interact with this fibrinolytic factor (Serrat *et al.*, 2025a). Notwithstanding the
522 limitations of using parasitic fibrinolysis-interacting proteins as vaccine targets, their applicability
523 has been explored in some trials. These employed proteins derived from the trematodes *F. hepatica*,
524 *S. japonicum*, *S. mansoni*, and *C. sinensis*, the nematode *Trichinella spiralis*, and the protozoans
525 *Babesia microti* and *B. bigenima*, yielding either variable or non-existent protection rates (**Table 1**).
526 Moreover, among these vaccination trials, those assessing vaccine efficacy in challenge infections
527 have been conducted in either mice or rats rather than in the definitive host species of the parasite,
528 meaning that their applicability to the affected population remains uncertain. Nonetheless, enolase
529 has been recently shown to be expressed at the tegument surface of *F. hepatica* juveniles, where it
530 interacts with PLG and stimulates plasmin generation (O’Kelly *et al.*, 2024). Although protection
531 rates have not yet been tested in challenge infections, this enolase isoform is recognised by sera from
532 experimentally-infected sheep, the natural host of this parasite, making it a potential vaccine
533 candidate against fasciolosis (O’Kelly *et al.*, 2024).

534

535 **Table 1. Vaccination trials using parasitic fibrinolysis-interacting proteins.**

Protein	Function	Parasite	Protection (a)	Method	Model	N (b)	Ref.
Annexin	PLG-R	<i>Clonorchis sinensis</i>	(c)	(c)	Rat		(He <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
Enolase	PLG-R	<i>Babesia microti</i>	Around 40%	Erythrocyte invasion, qRT-PCR	Mouse	4	(Liu <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
	PLG-R		24.28%	Egg count in liver	Mouse	10	

Protein	Function	Parasite	Protection (a)	Method	Model	N (b)	Ref.
		<i>Schistosoma japonicum</i>	21.45%	Egg count in faeces			(Yang <i>et al.</i> , 2010)
	PLG-R	<i>Babesia bigenima</i>	65%	Erythrocyte invasion	<i>In vitro</i> neutralisation assay	3	(Laura <i>et al.</i> , 2025)
	PLG-R	<i>Fasciola hepatica</i>	(c)	(c)	Sheep		(O’Kelly <i>et al.</i> , 2024)
FBAL	PLG-R	<i>Trichinella spiralis</i>	48.70%	Count of adult flukes in intestine	Mouse	25	(Yang <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
			52.50%	Count of larvae per gram of muscle			
PGM	PLG-R	<i>Schistosoma mansoni</i>	n.s.	Count of adults in portal vein	Mouse	10	(Pirovich <i>et al.</i> , 2024)
			n.s.	Egg count in liver			

536 Only parasitic proteins whose interaction with a component of the fibrinolytic system has been experimentally confirmed
537 are shown. (a) Percentage reduction in parasitic load during challenge infections in immunised animals compared to non-
538 immunised controls. (b) Number of animals employed per experimental group. (c) The study demonstrates that the
539 antigen is immunogenic but it does not address whether it protects against challenge infections. Blank cells indicate
540 information that was not provided or reported in the original publication. FBAL, fructose-1,6-bisphosphate aldolase;
541 PGM, phosphoglycerate mutase, PLG-R, plasminogen receptor; n.s., not significant.

542

543 An interesting aspect of the interaction between parasites and the host fibrinolytic system is
544 that it may underlie some of the pathogenesis linked to parasitic chronic infections. This is
545 particularly evident in cardiopulmonary dirofilariosis, a disease affecting primarily dogs and cats and
546 caused by infection with the nematode *D. immitis*. Adult worms reside in the pulmonary arteries and
547 right ventricle of the heart, where they can persist for years, eventually causing a chronic
548 inflammatory vascular pathology (González-Miguel *et al.*, 2015c). Plasmin generated as a result of
549 the recruitment of PLG at the surface of *D. immitis* stimulates the proliferation of canine endothelial
550 and smooth muscle cells, leading to proliferative endarteritis, the hallmark of cardiopulmonary
551 dirofilariosis (González-Miguel *et al.*, 2015a; b, 2016b). Similarly, cutaneous lesions associated to
552 *Leishmania mexicana* infection are smaller in mice with genetic depletion of PLG compared to their
553 WT littermates (Maldonado *et al.*, 2006); and the interaction between *F. hepatica* and host PLG has
554 been proposed to underlie the neurological disorders occasionally observed in human patients
555 (González-Miguel *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, parasites must carefully regulate the exploitation of the

556 host fibrinolytic system to balance the benefits that this interaction has to their survival with the long-
557 term pathogenic effects that excessive fibrinolysis may impose on the host (González-Miguel *et al.*,
558 2016a).

559 As evidenced by the present review, the arguments supporting the idea of the PLG/plasmin
560 system representing a key aspect to parasitic success are numerous; however, evidence coming from
561 physiologically-relevant experimental models to prove this point is still scarce. In this regard, a study
562 by Alves e Silva *et al.* using mouse models and a cutting-edge methodology convincingly
563 demonstrated that the interaction between *P. falciparum* and the host fibrinolytic system is required
564 for both the development of the parasite within its mosquito vector and the successful infection of
565 the mammalian host (Alves e Silva *et al.*, 2021). This interaction was also shown to have important
566 practical applications, as blocking the interaction between *P. falciparum* and PLG efficiently halted
567 parasitic development within the mosquito vector and transmission to mammalian hosts (Wang *et al.*,
568 2012; Pascini *et al.*, 2022). Similarly, the importance of the PLG/plasmin system in *F. hepatica*
569 infection has recently been underscored *in vivo* using a mouse model of early-stage fasciolosis (Serrat
570 *et al.*, 2025b). In addition to this, the importance of parasitic proteins that interact with the
571 PLG/plasmin system in infection success is supported by a proteomic study conducted in of
572 *Histomonas meleagridis*, a protozoan parasite of poultry (Monoyios *et al.*, 2018). This study revealed
573 that, in sharp contrast to their attenuated counterparts, virulent strains of *H. meleagridis* overexpress
574 proteins identified as canonical PLG-Rs in other parasite species, such as actin, GAPDH, and FBAL
575 (Monoyios *et al.*, 2018) (**Supp. File 2**), although the ability of the *H. meleagridis* homologs to bind
576 PLG has not been experimentally tested. In line with this, an enlightening study by Tritten *et al.*
577 revealed that some of the canonical fibrinolysis-interacting proteins identified in certain parasites
578 (e.g., enolase) are commonly present in ESPs of parasitic nematodes but not in those from the free-
579 living nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans* (Tritten *et al.*, 2021). Overall, a substantial body of evidence
580 supports the view that the interaction between parasites and the PLG/plasmin system plays a central
581 role in parasitic infections. Intriguingly, beyond facilitating parasite migration and immune

582 evasion—thereby increasing the likelihood of parasitic success—these data also suggest that co-
583 opting the functions of the host PLG/plasmin system may be a fundamental aspect of parasitism,
584 providing an exciting avenue for future research.

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593 **References**

- 594 **Acosta, H., Rondón-Mercado, R., Avilán, L. and Concepción, J. L.** (2016). Interaction of
595 *Trypanosoma evansi* with the plasminogen-plasmin system. *Veterinary Parasitology* **226**,
596 189–197. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2016.07.016>.
- 597 **Alberts, B., Heald, R., Johnson, A., Morgan, D., Raff, M., Roberts, K. and Walter, P.** (2022).
598 Chapter 22. Stem cells in tissue homeostasis and regeneration. In *Molecular Biology of the*
599 *Cell*, pp. 1279–1313. W. W. Norton & Company, New York.
- 600 **Al-Dasooqi, N., Wardill, H. R. and Gibson, R. J.** (2014). Gastrointestinal mucositis: the role of
601 MMP-tight junction interactions in tissue injury. *Pathology oncology research : POR* **20**,
602 485–491. doi: 10.1007/s12253-013-9733-y.

- 603 **Almeida, L., Vanegas, G., Calcagno, M., Concepción, J. L. and Avilan, L.** (2004). Plasminogen
604 interaction with *Trypanosoma cruzi*. *Memorias do Instituto Oswaldo Cruz* **99**, 63–67. doi:
605 10.1590/S0074-02762004000100011.
- 606 **Alves e Silva, T. L., Radtke, A., Balaban, A., Pascini, T. V., Pala, Z. R., Roth, A., Alvarenga, P.**
607 **H., Jeong, Y. J., Olivas, J., Ghosh, A. K., Bui, H., Pybus, B. S., Sinnis, P., Jacobs-Lorena,**
608 **M. and Vega-Rodríguez, J.** (2021). The fibrinolytic system enables the onset of *Plasmodium*
609 infection in the mosquito vector and the mammalian host. *Science advances* **7**,. doi:
610 10.1126/sciadv.abe3362.
- 611 **Andolfo, A., English, W. R., Resnati, M., Murphy, G., Blasi, F. and Sidenius, N.** (2002).
612 Metalloproteases cleave the urokinase-type plasminogen activator receptor in the D1-D2
613 linker region and expose epitopes not present in the intact soluble receptor. *Thrombosis and*
614 *haemostasis* **88**, 298–306.
- 615 **Ayón-Núñez, D. A., Frago, G., Bobes, R. J. and Laclette, J. P.** (2018). Plasminogen-binding
616 proteins as an evasion mechanism of the host's innate immunity in infectious diseases.
617 *Bioscience Reports* **38**, 1–16. doi: 10.1042/BSR20180705.
- 618 **Baker, S. K. and Strickland, S.** (2020). A critical role for plasminogen in inflammation. *The Journal*
619 *of experimental medicine* **217**,. doi: 10.1084/jem.20191865.
- 620 **Baramova, E. N., Bajou, K., Remacle, A., L'Hoir, C., Krell, H. W., Weidle, U. H., Noel, A. and**
621 **Foidart, J. M.** (1997). Involvement of PA/plasmin system in the processing of pro-MMP-9
622 and in the second step of pro-MMP-2 activation. *FEBS letters* **405**, 157–162. doi:
623 10.1016/s0014-5793(97)00175-0.
- 624 **Barrett, C. D., Moore, H. B., Banerjee, A., Silliman, C. C., Moore, E. E. and Yaffe, M. B.** (2017).
625 Human neutrophil elastase mediates fibrinolysis shutdown through competitive degradation

626 of plasminogen and generation of angiostatin. *The journal of trauma and acute care surgery*
627 **83**, 1053–1061. doi: 10.1097/TA.0000000000001685.

628 **Bhattacharya, S., Ploplis, V. A. and Castellino, F. J.** (2012). Bacterial plasminogen receptors
629 utilize host plasminogen system for effective invasion and dissemination. *Journal of*
630 *biomedicine & biotechnology* **2012**, 482096. doi: 10.1155/2012/482096.

631 **Boote-Wilbraham, C. A., Tazzyman, S., Thompson, W. D., Stirk, C. M. and Lewis, C. E.**
632 (2001). Fibrin fragment E stimulates the proliferation, migration and differentiation of human
633 microvascular endothelial cells in vitro. *Angiogenesis* **4**, 269–275. doi:
634 10.1023/a:1016076121918.

635 **Brauer, R., Beck, I. M., Roderfeld, M., Roeb, E. and Sedlacek, R.** (2011). Matrix
636 metalloproteinase-19 inhibits growth of endothelial cells by generating angiostatin-like
637 fragments from plasminogen. *BMC biochemistry* **12**, 38. doi: 10.1186/1471-2091-12-38.

638 **Cardoso, F. C., Macedo, G. C., Gava, E., Kitten, G. T., Mati, V. L., de Melo, A. L., Caliari, M.**
639 **V., Almeida, G. T., Venancio, T. M., Verjovski-Almeida, S. and Oliveira, S. C.** (2008).
640 *Schistosoma mansoni* tegument protein Sm29 is able to induce a Th1-type of immune
641 response and protection against parasite infection. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases* **2**, e308.
642 doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0000308.

643 **Carmeliet, P. and Jain, R. K.** (2011). Molecular mechanisms and clinical applications of
644 angiogenesis. *Nature* **473**, 298–307. doi: 10.1038/nature10144.

645 **Carmeliet, P., Moons, L., Lijnen, R., Baes, M., Lemaître, V., Tipping, P., Drew, A., Eeckhout,**
646 **Y., Shapiro, S., Lupu, F. and Collen, D.** (1997). Urokinase-generated plasmin activates
647 matrix metalloproteinases during aneurysm formation. *Nature genetics* **17**, 439–444. doi:
648 10.1038/ng1297-439.

- 649 **Carmen-Orozco, R. P., Dávila-Villacorta, D. G., Cauna, Y., Bernal-Teran, E. G., Bitterfeld, L.,**
650 **Sutherland, G. L., Chile, N., Céliz, R. H., Ferrufino-Schmidt, M. C., Gavídia, C. M.,**
651 **Sterling, C. R., García, H. H., Gilman, R. H. and Verástegui, M. R.** (2019). Blood-brain
652 barrier disruption and angiogenesis in a rat model for neurocysticercosis. *Journal of*
653 *neuroscience research* **97**, 137–148. doi: 10.1002/jnr.24335.
- 654 **Castellino, F. J. and Ploplis, V. A.** (2003). Human Plasminogen: Structure, Activation, and
655 Function. In *Plasminogen: Structure, Activation, and Regulation* (ed. Waisman, D. M.), pp.
656 3–17. Springer US, Boston, MA doi: 10.1007/978-1-4615-0165-7_1.
- 657 **Cauwe, B., Van den Steen, P. E. and Opdenakker, G.** (2007). The biochemical, biological, and
658 pathological kaleidoscope of cell surface substrates processed by matrix metalloproteinases.
659 *Critical reviews in biochemistry and molecular biology* **42**, 113–185. doi:
660 10.1080/10409230701340019.
- 661 **Cesarman-Maus, G. and Hajjar, K. A.** (2005). Molecular mechanisms of fibrinolysis. *British*
662 *Journal of Haematology* **129**, 307–321. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2141.2005.05444.x.
- 663 **Cha, S.-J., McLean, K. J. and Jacobs-Lorena, M.** (2018). Identification of Plasmodium GAPDH
664 epitopes for generation of antibodies that inhibit malaria infection. *Life Science Alliance* **1**,
665 doi: 10.26508/lsa.201800111.
- 666 **Chalmers, I. W., Fitzsimmons, C. M., Brown, M., Pierrot, C., Jones, F. M., Wawrzyniak, J. M.,**
667 **Fernandez-Fuentes, N., Tukahebwa, E. M., Dunne, D. W., Khalife, J. and Hoffmann, K.**
668 **F.** (2015). Human IgG1 Responses to Surface Localised *Schistosoma mansoni* Ly6 Family
669 Members Drop following Praziquantel Treatment. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases* **9**,
670 e0003920. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0003920.

- 671 **Chapman, H. A.** (1997). Plasminogen activators, integrins, and the coordinated regulation of cell
672 adhesion and migration. *Current opinion in cell biology* **9**, 714–724. doi: 10.1016/s0955-
673 0674(97)80126-3.
- 674 **Chen, S.-M., Zou, Z., Guo, S.-Y., Hou, W.-T., Qiu, X.-R., Zhang, Y., Song, L.-J., Hu, X.-Y.,**
675 **Jiang, Y.-Y., Shen, H. and An, M.-M.** (2020). Preventing *Candida albicans* from subverting
676 host plasminogen for invasive infection treatment. *Emerging microbes & infections* **9**, 2417–
677 2432. doi: 10.1080/22221751.2020.1840927.
- 678 **Chen, A.-C., Lai, S.-C., Lu, C.-Y. and Chen, K.-M.** (2024). Exploration of the Molecular
679 Mechanism by Which Caveolin-1 Regulates Changes in Blood-Brain Barrier Permeability
680 Leading to Eosinophilic Meningoencephalitis. *Tropical medicine and infectious disease* **9**,
681 doi: 10.3390/tropicalmed9060124.
- 682 **Cheng, Y., Hall, T. R., Xu, X., Yung, I., Souza, D., Zheng, J., Schiele, F., Hoffmann, M., Mbow,**
683 **M. L., Garnett, J. P. and Li, J.** (2022). Targeting uPA-uPAR interaction to improve
684 intestinal epithelial barrier integrity in inflammatory bowel disease. *eBioMedicine* **75**,
685 103758. doi: 10.1016/j.ebiom.2021.103758.
- 686 **Chou, C. S., Chou, M. C., Chen, K. M., Lu, C. Y. and Lai, S. C.** (2011). Induction of plasminogen
687 activators in pregnant women with *Toxoplasma gondii* infection. *Clinical and experimental*
688 *obstetrics & gynecology* **38**, 342–346.
- 689 **Chuba, J. V.** (1994). Susceptibility of monoclonal IgG paraproteins to plasminic cleavage using
690 glycerin-stabilized human plasmin. *Biochemical and biophysical research communications*
691 **202**, 367–373. doi: 10.1006/bbrc.1994.1937.
- 692 **Crane, D. D., Warner, S. L. and Bosio, C. M.** (2009). A novel role for plasmin-mediated
693 degradation of opsonizing antibody in the evasion of host immunity by virulent, but not

694 attenuated, *Francisella tularensis*. *Journal of immunology (Baltimore, Md. : 1950)* **183**, 4593–
695 4600. doi: 10.4049/jimmunol.0901655.

696 **Crowe, J. D., Sievwright, I. K., Auld, G. C., Moore, N. R., Gow, N. A. R. and Booth, N. A.**
697 (2003). *Candida albicans* binds human plasminogen: identification of eight plasminogen-
698 binding proteins. *Molecular microbiology* **47**, 1637–1651. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-
699 2958.2003.03390.x.

700 **Das, R., Ganapathy, S., Settle, M. and Plow, E. F.** (2014). Plasminogen promotes macrophage
701 phagocytosis in mice. *Blood* **124**, 679–688. doi: 10.1182/blood-2014-01-549659.

702 **Davey, S. D., Chalmers, I. W., Fernandez-Fuentes, N., Swain, M. T., Smith, D., Abbas Abidi, S.**
703 **M., Saifullah, M. K., Raman, M., Ravikumar, G., McVeigh, P., Maule, A. G., Brophy,**
704 **P. M. and Morphey, R. M.** (2022). In silico characterisation of the complete Ly6 protein
705 family in *Fasciola gigantica* supported through transcriptomics of the newly-excysted
706 juveniles. *Molecular omics* **18**, 45–56. doi: 10.1039/d1mo00254f.

707 **De Marco Verissimo, C., Jewhurst, H. L., Dobó, J., Gál, P., Dalton, J. P. and Cwiklinski, K.**
708 (2022). *Fasciola hepatica* is refractory to complement killing by preventing attachment of
709 mannose binding lectin (MBL) and inhibiting MBL-associated serine proteases (MASPs)
710 with serpins. *PLOS Pathogens* **18**, e1010226. doi: 10.1371/journal.ppat.1010226.

711 **Deng, G., Curriden, S. A., Wang, S., Rosenberg, S. and Loskutoff, D. J.** (1996). Is plasminogen
712 activator inhibitor-1 the molecular switch that governs urokinase receptor-mediated cell
713 adhesion and release? *The Journal of cell biology* **134**, 1563–1571. doi:
714 10.1083/jcb.134.6.1563.

715 **Dennis, R. D., Schubert, U. and Bauer, C.** (2011). Angiogenesis and parasitic helminth-associated
716 neovascularization. *Parasitology* **138**, 426–439. doi: 10.1017/S0031182010001642.

717 **Dewerchin, M., Nuffelen, A. V., Wallays, G., Bouché, A., Moons, L., Carmeliet, P., Mulligan,**
718 **R. C. and Collen, D.** (1996). Generation and characterization of urokinase receptor-deficient
719 mice. *The Journal of clinical investigation* **97**, 870–878. doi: 10.1172/JCI118489.

720 **Di Maggio, L. S., Tirloni, L., Pinto, A. F. M., Diedrich, J. K., Yates Iii, J. R., Benavides, U.,**
721 **Carmona, C., da Silva Vaz, I. J. and Berasain, P.** (2016). Across intra-mammalian stages
722 of the liver fluke *Fasciola hepatica*: a proteomic study. *Scientific reports* **6**, 32796. doi:
723 10.1038/srep32796.

724 **Diosdado, A., Simón, F., Serrat, J. and González-Miguel, J.** (2022). Interaction of helminth
725 parasites with the haemostatic system of their vertebrate hosts: a scoping review. *Parasite* **29**,
726 35. doi: 10.1051/parasite/2022034.

727 **Draxler, D. F. and Medcalf, R. L.** (2015). The fibrinolytic system-more than fibrinolysis?
728 *Transfusion medicine reviews* **29**, 102–109. doi: 10.1016/j.tmr.2014.09.006.

729 **Draxler, D. F., Sashindranath, M. and Medcalf, R. L.** (2017). Plasmin: A Modulator of Immune
730 Function. *Seminars in thrombosis and hemostasis* **43**, 143–153. doi: 10.1055/s-0036-
731 1586227.

732 **El Chamy Maluf, S., Icimoto, M. Y., Melo, P. M. S., Budu, A., Coimbra, R., Gazarini, M. L.**
733 **and Carmona, A. K.** (2020). Human plasma plasminogen internalization route in
734 *Plasmodium falciparum*-infected erythrocytes. *Malaria journal* **19**, 302. doi:
735 10.1186/s12936-020-03377-4.

736 **Endsley, M. P., Hu, Y., Deng, Y., He, X., Warejcka, D. J., Twining, S. S., Gonias, S. L. and**
737 **Zhang, M.** (2011). Maspin, the molecular bridge between the plasminogen activator system
738 and beta1 integrin that facilitates cell adhesion. *The Journal of biological chemistry* **286**,
739 24599–24607. doi: 10.1074/jbc.M111.235788.

- 740 **Ernest, M., Rosa, T. F. A., Pala, Z. R., Kudyba, H. M., Sweeney, B., Reiss, T., Pradel, G. and**
741 **Vega-Rodríguez, J.** (2023). Plasmodium falciparum Gametes and Sporozoites Hijack
742 Plasmin and Factor H To Evade Host Complement Killing. *Microbiology spectrum* **11**,
743 e0449322. doi: 10.1128/spectrum.04493-22.
- 744 **Farina, A. R., Tacconelli, A., Cappabianca, L., Gulino, A. and Mackay, A. R.** (2002). Inhibition
745 of human MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cell invasion by matrix metalloproteinase 3 involves
746 degradation of plasminogen. *European journal of biochemistry* **269**, 4476–4483. doi:
747 10.1046/j.1432-1033.2002.03142.x.
- 748 **Fauser, S., Deininger, M. H., Kremsner, P. G., Magdolen, V., Luther, T., Meyermann, R. and**
749 **Schluesener, H. J.** (2000). Lesion associated expression of urokinase-type plasminogen
750 activator receptor (uPAR, CD87) in human cerebral malaria. *Journal of Neuroimmunology*
751 **111**, 234–240. doi: 10.1016/S0165-5728(00)00368-4.
- 752 **Feng, M. and Cheng, X.** (2017). Parasite-Associated Cancers (Blood Flukes/Liver Flukes).
753 *Advances in experimental medicine and biology* **1018**, 193–205. doi: 10.1007/978-981-10-
754 5765-6_12.
- 755 **Ferraris, G. M. S. and Sidenius, N.** (2013). Urokinase plasminogen activator receptor: a functional
756 integrator of extracellular proteolysis, cell adhesion, and signal transduction. *Seminars in*
757 *thrombosis and hemostasis* **39**, 347–355. doi: 10.1055/s-0033-1334485.
- 758 **Festuccia, C., Giunciuglio, D., Guerra, F., Villanova, I., Angelucci, A., Manduca, P., Teti, A.,**
759 **Albini, A. and Bologna, M.** (1999). Osteoblasts modulate secretion of urokinase-type
760 plasminogen activator (uPA) and matrix metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9) in human prostate
761 cancer cells promoting migration and matrigel invasion. *Oncology research* **11**, 17–31.

- 762 **Figueiredo, B. C., Da'dara, A. A., Oliveira, S. C. and Skelly, P. J.** (2015). Schistosomes Enhance
763 Plasminogen Activation: The Role of Tegumental Enolase. *PLoS pathogens* **11**, e1005335.
764 doi: 10.1371/journal.ppat.1005335.
- 765 **Flick, M. J., Du, X., Witte, D. P., Jirousková, M., Soloviev, D. A., Busuttil, S. J., Plow, E. F. and**
766 **Degen, J. L.** (2004). Leukocyte engagement of fibrin(ogen) via the integrin receptor
767 alphaMbeta2/Mac-1 is critical for host inflammatory response in vivo. *The Journal of clinical*
768 *investigation* **113**, 1596–1606. doi: 10.1172/JCI20741.
- 769 **Foley, J. H.** (2017). Plasmin(ogen) at the Nexus of Fibrinolysis, Inflammation, and Complement.
770 *Seminars in thrombosis and hemostasis* **43**, 135–142. doi: 10.1055/s-0036-1592302.
- 771 **Fredriksson, L., Li, H., Fieber, C., Li, X. and Eriksson, U.** (2004). Tissue plasminogen activator
772 is a potent activator of PDGF-CC. *The EMBO journal* **23**, 3793–3802. doi:
773 10.1038/sj.emboj.7600397.
- 774 **Gause, W. C., Wynn, T. A. and Allen, J. E.** (2013). Type 2 immunity and wound healing:
775 evolutionary refinement of adaptive immunity by helminths. *Nature reviews. Immunology* **13**,
776 607–614. doi: 10.1038/nri3476.
- 777 **Ghosh, A. K. and Jacobs-Lorena, M.** (2011). Surface-expressed enolases of Plasmodium and other
778 pathogens. *Memorias do Instituto Oswaldo Cruz* **106 Suppl 1**, 85–90. doi: 10.1590/s0074-
779 02762011000900011.
- 780 **Gibson, P. R., Birchall, I., Rosella, O., Albert, V., Finch, C. F., Barkla, D. H. and Young, G. P.**
781 (1998). Urokinase and the intestinal mucosa: evidence for a role in epithelial cell turnover.
782 *Gut* **43**, 656–663. doi: 10.1136/gut.43.5.656.

- 783 **Gong, Y., Hart, E., Shchurin, A. and Hoover-Plow, J.** (2008). Inflammatory macrophage
784 migration requires MMP-9 activation by plasminogen in mice. *The Journal of clinical*
785 *investigation* **118**, 3012–3024. doi: 10.1172/JCI32750.
- 786 **González-Miguel, J., Morchón, R., Carretón, E., Montoya-Alonso, J. A. and Simón, F.** (2013).
787 Surface associated antigens of *Dirofilaria immitis* adult worms activate the host fibrinolytic
788 system. *Veterinary parasitology* **196**, 235–240. doi: 10.1016/j.vetpar.2013.01.028.
- 789 **González-Miguel, J., Morchón, R., Siles-Lucas, M. and Simón, F.** (2015a). Fibrinolysis and
790 proliferative endarteritis: two related processes in chronic infections? The model of the blood-
791 borne pathogen *Dirofilaria immitis*. *PloS one* **10**, e0124445. doi:
792 10.1371/journal.pone.0124445.
- 793 **González-Miguel, J., Morchón, R., Carretón, E., Montoya-Alonso, J. A. and Simón, F.** (2015b).
794 Can the activation of plasminogen/plasmin system of the host by metabolic products of
795 *Dirofilaria immitis* participate in heartworm disease endarteritis? *Parasites & vectors* **8**, 194.
796 doi: 10.1186/s13071-015-0799-0.
- 797 **González-Miguel, J., Morchón, R., Siles-Lucas, M., Oleaga, A. and Simón, F.** (2015c). Surface-
798 displayed glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase and galectin from *Dirofilaria immitis*
799 enhance the activation of the fibrinolytic system of the host. *Acta tropica* **145**, 8–16. doi:
800 10.1016/j.actatropica.2015.01.010.
- 801 **González-Miguel, J., Siles-Lucas, M., Kartashev, V., Morchón, R. and Simón, F.** (2016a).
802 Plasmin in Parasitic Chronic Infections: Friend or Foe? *Trends in Parasitology* **32**, 325–335.
803 doi: 10.1016/j.pt.2015.12.012.
- 804 **González-Miguel, J., Larrazabal, C., Loa-Mesón, D., Siles-Lucas, M., Simón, F. and Morchón,**
805 **R.** (2016b). Glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase and galectin from *Dirofilaria*

806 immitis participate in heartworm disease endarteritis via plasminogen/plasmin system.
807 *Veterinary parasitology* **223**, 96–101. doi: 10.1016/j.vetpar.2016.04.029.

808 **González-Miguel, J., Valero, M. A., Reguera-Gomez, M., Mas-Bargues, C., Bargues, M. D.,**
809 **Simón, F. and Mas-Coma, S.** (2019). Numerous *Fasciola* plasminogen-binding proteins
810 may underlie blood-brain barrier leakage and explain neurological disorder complexity and
811 heterogeneity in the acute and chronic phases of human fascioliasis. *Parasitology* **146**, 284–
812 298. doi: 10.1017/S0031182018001464.

813 **Gyetko, M. R., Sud, S., Kendall, T., Fuller, J. A., Newstead, M. W. and Standiford, T. J.** (2000).
814 Urokinase receptor-deficient mice have impaired neutrophil recruitment in response to
815 pulmonary *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* infection. *Journal of immunology (Baltimore, Md. :
816 1950)* **165**, 1513–1519. doi: 10.4049/jimmunol.165.3.1513.

817 **Hahn-Dantona, E., Ramos-DeSimone, N., Siple, J., Nagase, H., French, D. L. and Quigley, J.**
818 **P.** (1999). Activation of proMMP-9 by a plasmin/MMP-3 cascade in a tumor cell model.
819 Regulation by tissue inhibitors of metalloproteinases. *Annals of the New York Academy of
820 Sciences* **878**, 372–387. doi: 10.1111/j.1749-6632.1999.tb07696.x.

821 **Hamada, M., Varkoly, K. S., Riyadh, O., Beladi, R., Munuswamy-Ramanujam, G., Rawls, A.,**
822 **Wilson-Rawls, J., Chen, H., McFadden, G. and Lucas, A. R.** (2024). Urokinase-Type
823 Plasminogen Activator Receptor (uPAR) in Inflammation and Disease: A Unique
824 Inflammatory Pathway Activator. *Biomedicines* **12**,. doi: 10.3390/biomedicines12061167.

825 **He, L., Ren, M., Chen, X., Wang, X., Li, S., Lin, J., Liang, C., Liang, P., Hu, Y., Lei, H., Bian,**
826 **M., Huang, Y., Wu, Z., Li, X. and Yu, X.** (2014). Biochemical and immunological
827 characterization of annexin B30 from *Clonorchis sinensis* excretory/secretory products.
828 *Parasitology research* **113**, 2743–2755. doi: 10.1007/s00436-014-3935-4.

- 829 **Heggi, M. T., Nour El-Din, H. T., Morsy, D. I., Abdelaziz, N. I. and Attia, A. S.** (2024). Microbial
830 evasion of the complement system: a continuous and evolving story. *Frontiers in immunology*
831 **14**, 1281096. doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2023.1281096.
- 832 **Hoffman, R., Starkey, S. and Coad, J.** (1998). Wound fluid from venous leg ulcers degrades
833 plasminogen and reduces plasmin generation by keratinocytes. *The Journal of investigative*
834 *dermatology* **111**, 1140–1144. doi: 10.1046/j.1523-1747.1998.00429.x.
- 835 **Hu, K., Yang, J., Tanaka, S., Gonias, S. L., Mars, W. M. and Liu, Y.** (2006). Tissue-type
836 plasminogen activator acts as a cytokine that triggers intracellular signal transduction and
837 induces matrix metalloproteinase-9 gene expression. *The Journal of biological chemistry* **281**,
838 2120–2127. doi: 10.1074/jbc.M504988200.
- 839 **Ishihara, M., Nishida, C., Tashiro, Y., Gritli, I., Rosenkvist, J., Koizumi, M., Okaji, Y.,**
840 **Yamamoto, R., Yagita, H., Okumura, K., Nishikori, M., Wanaka, K., Tsuda, Y., Okada,**
841 **Y., Nakauchi, H., Heissig, B. and Hattori, K.** (2012). Plasmin inhibitor reduces T-cell
842 lymphoid tumor growth by suppressing matrix metalloproteinase-9-dependent
843 CD11b(+)/F4/80(+) myeloid cell recruitment. *Leukemia* **26**, 332–339. doi:
844 10.1038/leu.2011.203.
- 845 **Ismail, A. A., Shaker, B. T. and Bajou, K.** (2021). The Plasminogen-Activator Plasmin System in
846 Physiological and Pathophysiological Angiogenesis. *International journal of molecular*
847 *sciences* **23**,. doi: 10.3390/ijms23010337.
- 848 **Jennewein, C., Tran, N., Paulus, P., Ellinghaus, P., Eble, J. A. and Zacharowski, K.** (2011).
849 Novel Aspects of Fibrin(ogen) Fragments during Inflammation. *Molecular Medicine* **17**,
850 568–573. doi: 10.2119/molmed.2010.00146.

851 **Kanse, S. M., Kost, C., Wilhelm, O. G., Andreasen, P. A. and Preissner, K. T.** (1996). The
852 urokinase receptor is a major vitronectin-binding protein on endothelial cells. *Experimental*
853 *cell research* **224**, 344–353. doi: 10.1006/excr.1996.0144.

854 **Keene, W. E., Petitt, M. G., Allen, S. and McKerrow, J. H.** (1986). The major neutral proteinase
855 of *Entamoeba histolytica*. *The Journal of experimental medicine* **163**, 536–549. doi:
856 10.1084/jem.163.3.536.

857 **Keski-Oja, J., Lohi, J., Tuuttila, A., Tryggvason, K. and Vartio, T.** (1992). Proteolytic processing
858 of the 72,000-Da type IV collagenase by urokinase plasminogen activator. *Experimental cell*
859 *research* **202**, 471–476. doi: 10.1016/0014-4827(92)90101-d.

860 **Koolwijk, P., Sidenius, N., Peters, E., Sier, C. F., Hanemaaijer, R., Blasi, F. and van Hinsbergh,**
861 **V. W.** (2001). Proteolysis of the urokinase-type plasminogen activator receptor by
862 metalloproteinase-12: implication for angiogenesis in fibrin matrices. *Blood* **97**, 3123–3131.
863 doi: 10.1182/blood.v97.10.3123.

864 **Lan, K. P. and Lai, S. C.** (2009). Differences of proteolytic enzymes and pathological changes in
865 permissive and nonpermissive animal hosts for *Angiostrongylus cantonensis* infection.
866 *Veterinary parasitology* **165**, 265–272. doi: 10.1016/j.vetpar.2009.07.029.

867 **Laura, L.-R. A., Juan, M., Jacqueline, C.-O. E., Mariana, A.-I., Alma, C.-F., Valeria**
868 **Guadalupe, D. L. C. G., Elizabeth, Á.-S. M. and Minerva, C.-N.** (2025). *Babesia bigemina*
869 enolase binds to plasminogen and contains conserved B-cell epitopes that induce neutralizing
870 antibodies in cattle. *Veterinary parasitology* **337**, 110503. doi: 10.1016/j.vetpar.2025.110503.

871 **Leduc, D., Beaufort, N., de Bentzmann, S., Rousselle, J.-C., Namane, A., Chignard, M. and**
872 **Pidard, D.** (2007). The *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* LasB metalloproteinase regulates the
873 human urokinase-type plasminogen activator receptor through domain-specific
874 endoproteolysis. *Infection and immunity* **75**, 3848–3858. doi: 10.1128/IAI.00015-07.

- 875 **Legrand, C., Polette, M., Tournier, J. M., de Bentzmann, S., Huet, E., Monteau, M. and**
876 **Birembaut, P.** (2001). uPA/plasmin system-mediated MMP-9 activation is implicated in
877 bronchial epithelial cell migration. *Experimental cell research* **264**, 326–336. doi:
878 10.1006/excr.2000.5125.
- 879 **Leontovyč, A., Ulrychová, L., O'Donoghue, A. J., Vondrášek, J., Marešová, L., Hubálek, M.,**
880 **Fajtová, P., Chanová, M., Jiang, Z., Craik, C. S., Caffrey, C. R., Mareš, M., Dvořák, J.**
881 **and Horn, M.** (2018). SmSP2: A serine protease secreted by the blood fluke pathogen
882 *Schistosoma mansoni* with anti-hemostatic properties. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases* **12**,
883 e0006446. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0006446.
- 884 **Li, W.-Y., Chong, S. S. N., Huang, E. Y. and Tuan, T.-L.** (2003). Plasminogen activator/plasmin
885 system: a major player in wound healing? *Wound repair and regeneration: official*
886 *publication of the Wound Healing Society [and] the European Tissue Repair Society* **11**, 239–
887 247. doi: 10.1046/j.1524-475x.2003.11402.x.
- 888 **Lijnen, H. R.** (2001a). Elements of the Fibrinolytic System. *Annals of the New York Academy of*
889 *Sciences* **936**, 226–236. doi: 10.1111/j.1749-6632.2001.tb03511.x.
- 890 **Lijnen, H. R.** (2001b). Plasmin and matrix metalloproteinases in vascular remodeling. *Thrombosis*
891 *and haemostasis* **86**, 324–333.
- 892 **Lijnen, H. R., Ugwu, F., Bini, A. and Collen, D.** (1998). Generation of an angiostatin-like fragment
893 from plasminogen by stromelysin-1 (MMP-3). *Biochemistry* **37**, 4699–4702. doi:
894 10.1021/bi9731798.
- 895 **Lin, L., Gårdsvoll, H., Huai, Q., Huang, M. and Ploug, M.** (2010). Structure-based Engineering
896 of Species Selectivity in the Interaction between Urokinase and Its Receptor. *Journal of*
897 *Biological Chemistry* **285**, 10982–10992. doi: 10.1074/jbc.M109.093492.

- 898 **Liu, X., Zheng, C., Gao, X., Chen, J. and Zheng, K.** (2017). Complete Molecular and
899 Immunoprotective Characterization of Babesia microti Enolase. *Frontiers in microbiology* **8**,
900 622. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2017.00622.
- 901 **Loef, E. J., Sheppard, H. M., Birch, N. P. and Dunbar, P. R.** (2022). Plasminogen and plasmin
902 can bind to human T cells and generate truncated CCL21 that increases dendritic cell
903 chemotactic responses. *The Journal of biological chemistry* **298**, 102112. doi:
904 10.1016/j.jbc.2022.102112.
- 905 **Lothstein, K. E., Chen, F., Mishra, P., Smyth, D. J., Wu, W., Lemenze, A., Kumamoto, Y.,**
906 **Maizels, R. M. and Gause, W. C.** (2024). Helminth protein enhances wound healing by
907 inhibiting fibrosis and promoting tissue regeneration. *Life science alliance* **7**,. doi:
908 10.26508/lsa.202302249.
- 909 **Magali de Bruyn, S. V., Jennifer Vandooren, Estefania Ugarte-Berzal, Ingrid Arijs and**
910 **Opdenakker, G.** (2016). The molecular biology of matrix metalloproteinases and tissue
911 inhibitors of metalloproteinases in inflammatory bowel diseases. *Critical Reviews in*
912 *Biochemistry and Molecular Biology* **51**, 295–358. doi: 10.1080/10409238.2016.1199535.
- 913 **Maizels, R. M. and McSorley, H. J.** (2016). Regulation of the host immune system by helminth
914 parasites. *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology* **138**, 666–675. doi:
915 10.1016/j.jaci.2016.07.007.
- 916 **Maldonado, J., Marina, C., Puig, J., Maizo, Z. and Avilan, L.** (2006). A study of cutaneous lesions
917 caused by Leishmania mexicana in plasminogen-deficient mice. *Experimental and molecular*
918 *pathology* **80**, 289–294. doi: 10.1016/j.yexmp.2005.06.005.
- 919 **Marcos-Contreras, O. A., Martinez de Lizarrondo, S., Bardou, I., Orset, C., Pruvost, M.,**
920 **Anfray, A., Frigout, Y., Hommet, Y., Lebouvier, L., Montaner, J., Vivien, D. and**
921 **Gauberti, M.** (2016). Hyperfibrinolysis increases blood-brain barrier permeability by a

922 plasmin- and bradykinin-dependent mechanism. *Blood* **128**, 2423–2434. doi: 10.1182/blood-
923 2016-03-705384.

924 **Mas-Coma, S., Agramunt, V. H. and Valero, M. A.** (2014). Neurological and Ocular Fascioliasis
925 in Humans. In *Advances in Parasitology*, pp. 27–149. Elsevier doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-
926 800099-1.00002-8.

927 **Mattos, E. C., Schumacher, R. I., Colli, W. and Alves, M. J. M.** (2012). Adhesion of Trypanosoma
928 cruzi Trypomastigotes to Fibronectin or Laminin Modifies Tubulin and Paraflagellar Rod
929 Protein Phosphorylation. *PLoS ONE* **7**, e46767. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0046767.

930 **Mattos, E. C., Canuto, G., Manchola, N. C., Magalhães, R. D. M., Crozier, T. W. M., Lamont,
931 D. J., Tavares, M. F. M., Colli, W., Ferguson, M. A. J. and Alves, M. J. M.** (2019).
932 Reprogramming of Trypanosoma cruzi metabolism triggered by parasite interaction with the
933 host cell extracellular matrix. *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases* **13**, e0007103. doi:
934 10.1371/journal.pntd.0007103.

935 **Mazar, A. P., Henkin, J. and Goldfarb, R. H.** (1999). The urokinase plasminogen activator system
936 in cancer: implications for tumor angiogenesis and metastasis. *Angiogenesis* **3**, 15–32. doi:
937 10.1023/a:1009095825561.

938 **McGwire, B. S., Chang, K.-P. and Engman, D. M.** (2003). Migration through the extracellular
939 matrix by the parasitic protozoan Leishmania is enhanced by surface metalloprotease gp63.
940 *Infection and immunity* **71**, 1008–1010. doi: 10.1128/IAI.71.2.1008-1010.2003.

941 **Medcalf, R. L. and Keragala, C. B.** (2021). Fibrinolysis: A Primordial System Linked to the
942 Immune Response. *International journal of molecular sciences* **22**,. doi:
943 10.3390/ijms22073406.

- 944 **Melo, P. M. S., Bagnaresi, P., Paschoalin, T., Hirata, I. Y., Gazarini, M. L. and Carmona, A. K.**
945 (2014). Plasmodium falciparum proteases hydrolyze plasminogen, generating angiostatin-
946 like fragments. *Molecular and biochemical parasitology* **193**, 45–54. doi:
947 10.1016/j.molbiopara.2014.01.004.
- 948 **Miles, L. A., Ny, L., Wilczynska, M., Shen, Y., Ny, T. and Parmer, R. J.** (2021). Plasminogen
949 Receptors and Fibrinolysis. *International journal of molecular sciences* **22**,. doi:
950 10.3390/ijms22041712.
- 951 **Monoyios, A., Hummel, K., Nöbauer, K., Patzl, M., Schlosser, S., Hess, M. and Bilic, I.** (2018).
952 An Alliance of Gel-Based and Gel-Free Proteomic Techniques Displays Substantial Insight
953 Into the Proteome of a Virulent and an Attenuated *Histomonas meleagridis* Strain. *Frontiers*
954 *in cellular and infection microbiology* **8**, 407. doi: 10.3389/fcimb.2018.00407.
- 955 **Moritake, A., Kawao, N., Okada, K., Ishida, M., Tatsumi, K., Matsuo, O., Akagi, M. and Kaji,**
956 **H.** (2019). Plasminogen activator inhibitor-1 is involved in interleukin-1 β -induced matrix
957 metalloproteinase expression in murine chondrocytes. *Modern rheumatology* **29**, 959–963.
958 doi: 10.1080/14397595.2018.1525018.
- 959 **Moser, T. L., Enghild, J. J., Pizzo, S. V. and Stack, M. S.** (1993). The extracellular matrix proteins
960 laminin and fibronectin contain binding domains for human plasminogen and tissue
961 plasminogen activator. *The Journal of biological chemistry* **268**, 18917–18923.
- 962 **Mubarak, M. M., Baba, I. A., Wani, Z. A., Kantroo, H. A. and Ahmad, Z.** (2025). Matrix
963 metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9): A macromolecular mediator in CNS infections: A review.
964 *International journal of biological macromolecules* **311**, 143902. doi:
965 10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.143902.
- 966 **Mulvenna, J., Sripa, B., Brindley, P. J., Gorman, J., Jones, M. K., Colgrave, M. L., Jones, A.,**
967 **Nawaratna, S., Laha, T., Suttiprapa, S., Smout, M. J. and Loukas, A.** (2010). The secreted

968 and surface proteomes of the adult stage of the carcinogenic human liver fluke *Opisthorchis*
969 *viverrini*. *Proteomics* **10**, 1063–1078. doi: 10.1002/pmic.200900393.

970 **Nowak, M. A., Boerlijst, M. C., Cooke, J. and Smith, J. M.** (1997). Evolution of genetic
971 redundancy. *Nature* **388**, 167–171. doi: 10.1038/40618.

972 **Okada, Y., Gonoji, Y., Naka, K., Tomita, K., Nakanishi, I., Iwata, K., Yamashita, K. and**
973 **Hayakawa, T.** (1992). Matrix metalloproteinase 9 (92-kDa gelatinase/type IV collagenase)
974 from HT 1080 human fibrosarcoma cells. Purification and activation of the precursor and
975 enzymic properties. *The Journal of biological chemistry* **267**, 21712–21719.

976 **Okada, K., Ueshima, S., Kawao, N., Yano, M., Tamura, Y., Tanaka, M., Sakamoto, A., Hatano,**
977 **M., Arima, M., Miyata, S., Nagai, N., Tokuhisa, T. and Matsuo, O.** (2013). Lack of both
978 α 2-antiplasmin and plasminogen activator inhibitor type-1 induces high IgE production. *Life*
979 *Sciences* **93**, 89–95. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lfs.2013.05.023>.

980 **O’Kelly, E., Cwiklinski, K., De Marco Verissimo, C., Calvani, N. E. D., López Corrales, J.,**
981 **Jewhurst, H., Flaus, A., Lalor, R., Serrat, J., Dalton, J. P. and González-Miguel, J.**
982 (2024). Moonlighting on the *Fasciola hepatica* tegument: Enolase, a glycolytic enzyme,
983 interacts with the extracellular matrix and fibrinolytic system of the host. *PLoS neglected*
984 *tropical diseases* **18**, e0012069. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0012069.

985 **Orbe, J., Rodríguez, J. A., Calvayrac, O., Rodríguez-Calvo, R., Rodríguez, C., Roncal, C.,**
986 **Martínez de Lizarrondo, S., Barrenetxe, J., Reverter, J. C., Martínez-González, J. and**
987 **Páramo, J. A.** (2009). Matrix metalloproteinase-10 is upregulated by thrombin in endothelial
988 cells and increased in patients with enhanced thrombin generation. *Arteriosclerosis,*
989 *thrombosis, and vascular biology* **29**, 2109–2116. doi: 10.1161/ATVBAHA.109.194589.

990 **Orbe, J., Barrenetxe, J., Rodriguez, J. A., Vivien, D., Orset, C., Parks, W. C., Birkland, T. P.,**
991 **Serrano, R., Purroy, A., Martinez de Lizarrondo, S., Angles-Cano, E. and Páramo, J.**

- 992 A. (2011). Matrix metalloproteinase-10 effectively reduces infarct size in experimental stroke
993 by enhancing fibrinolysis via a thrombin-activatable fibrinolysis inhibitor-mediated
994 mechanism. *Circulation* **124**, 2909–2919. doi: 10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.111.047100.
- 995 **Pagliari, V., Adornetto, A., Mammi, M., Masullo, M., Sarnataro, D., Pietropaolo, C. and**
996 **Arcone, R.** (2014). Protease Nexin-1 affects the migration and invasion of C6 glioma cells
997 through the regulation of urokinase Plasminogen Activator and Matrix Metalloproteinase-
998 9/2. *Biochimica et biophysica acta* **1843**, 2631–2644. doi: 10.1016/j.bbamcr.2014.07.008.
- 999 **Pala, Z. R., Ernest, M., Sweeney, B., Jeong, Y. J., Pascini, T. V., Alves E Silva, T. L. and Vega-**
1000 **Rodríguez, J.** (2022). Beyond cuts and scrapes: plasmin in malaria and other vector-borne
1001 diseases. *Trends in Parasitology* **38**, 147–159. doi: 10.1016/j.pt.2021.09.008.
- 1002 **Pan, P., Li, G., Shen, M., Yu, Z., Ge, W., Lao, Z., Fan, Y., Chen, K., Ding, Z., Wang, W., Wan,**
1003 **P., Shereen, M. A., Luo, Z., Chen, X., Zhang, Q., Lin, L. and Wu, J.** (2021). DENV NS1
1004 and MMP-9 cooperate to induce vascular leakage by altering endothelial cell adhesion and
1005 tight junction. *PLoS pathogens* **17**, e1008603. doi: 10.1371/journal.ppat.1008603.
- 1006 **Papasergi, S., Garibaldi, M., Tuscano, G., Signorino, G., Ricci, S., Peppoloni, S., Pernice, I., Lo**
1007 **Passo, C., Teti, G., Felici, F. and Beninati, C.** (2010). Plasminogen- and fibronectin-binding
1008 protein B is involved in the adherence of *Streptococcus pneumoniae* to human epithelial cells.
1009 *The Journal of biological chemistry* **285**, 7517–7524. doi: 10.1074/jbc.M109.062075.
- 1010 **Park, E. J., Myint, P. K., Ito, A., Appiah, M. G., Darkwah, S., Kawamoto, E. and Shimaoka,**
1011 **M.** (2020). Integrin-Ligand Interactions in Inflammation, Cancer, and Metabolic Disease:
1012 Insights Into the Multifaceted Roles of an Emerging Ligand Irisin. *Frontiers in cell and*
1013 *developmental biology* **8**, 588066. doi: 10.3389/fcell.2020.588066.
- 1014 **Pascini, T. V., Jeong, Y. J., Huang, W., Pala, Z. R., Sá, J. M., Wells, M. B., Kizito, C., Sweeney,**
1015 **B., Alves E Silva, T. L., Andrew, D. J., Jacobs-Lorena, M. and Vega-Rodríguez, J.**

1016 (2022). Transgenic *Anopheles* mosquitoes expressing human PAI-1 impair malaria
1017 transmission. *Nature communications* **13**, 2949. doi: 10.1038/s41467-022-30606-y.

1018 **Pastore, S., Mascia, F., Mariani, V. and Girolomoni, G.** (2008). The epidermal growth factor
1019 receptor system in skin repair and inflammation. *The Journal of investigative dermatology*
1020 **128**, 1365–1374. doi: 10.1038/sj.jid.5701184.

1021 **Pepper, M. S.** (2001). Role of the matrix metalloproteinase and plasminogen activator-plasmin
1022 systems in angiogenesis. *Arteriosclerosis, thrombosis, and vascular biology* **21**, 1104–1117.
1023 doi: 10.1161/hq0701.093685.

1024 **Pereira-Filho, A. A., Queiroz, D. C., Saab, N. A. A., D'Ávila Pessoa, G. C., Koerich, L. B.,**
1025 **Pereira, M. H., Sant'Anna, M. R. V., Araújo, R. N., Bartholomeu, D. C. and Gontijo, N.**
1026 **F.** (2023). Evasion of the complement system by *Leishmania* through the uptake of C4bBP,
1027 a complement regulatory protein, and probably by the action of GP63 on C4b molecules
1028 deposited on parasite surface. *Acta tropica* **242**, 106908. doi:
1029 10.1016/j.actatropica.2023.106908.

1030 **Perucci, L. O., Vago, J. P., Miles, L. A. and Sousa, L. P.** (2023). Crosstalk between the
1031 plasminogen/plasmin system and inflammation resolution. *Journal of thrombosis and*
1032 *haemostasis : JTH* **21**, 2666–2678. doi: 10.1016/j.jtha.2023.07.013.

1033 **Pirovich, D. B., Da'dara, A. A. and Skelly, P. J.** (2024). GLYCOLYTIC ENZYMES AS
1034 VACCINES AGAINST SCHISTOSOMIASIS: TESTING SCHISTOSOMA MANSONI
1035 PHOSPHOGLYCERATE MUTASE IN MICE. *The Journal of parasitology* **110**, 96–105.
1036 doi: 10.1645/23-7.

1037 **Ploplis, V. A., French, E. L., Carmeliet, P., Collen, D. and Plow, E. F.** (1998). Plasminogen
1038 deficiency differentially affects recruitment of inflammatory cell populations in mice. *Blood*
1039 **91**, 2005–2009.

- 1040 **Plouët, J., Moro, F., Bertagnolli, S., Coldeboeuf, N., Mazarguil, H., Clamens, S. and Bayard, F.**
1041 (1997). Extracellular Cleavage of the Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor 189-Amino Acid
1042 Form by Urokinase Is Required for Its Mitogenic Effect*. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*
1043 **272**, 13390–13396. doi: 10.1074/jbc.272.20.13390.
- 1044 **Pompili, S., Latella, G., Gaudio, E., Sferra, R. and Vetuschi, A.** (2021). The Charming World of
1045 the Extracellular Matrix: A Dynamic and Protective Network of the Intestinal Wall. *Frontiers*
1046 *in Medicine* **8**, 610189. doi: 10.3389/fmed.2021.610189.
- 1047 **Ramos-DeSimone, N., Hahn-Dantona, E., Siple, J., Nagase, H., French, D. L. and Quigley, J.**
1048 **P.** (1999). Activation of matrix metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9) via a converging
1049 plasmin/stromelysin-1 cascade enhances tumor cell invasion. *The Journal of biological*
1050 *chemistry* **274**, 13066–13076. doi: 10.1074/jbc.274.19.13066.
- 1051 **Read, A. F. and Skorpung, A.** (1995). The evolution of tissue migration by parasitic nematode
1052 larvae. *Parasitology* **111 (Pt 3)**, 359–371. doi: 10.1017/s0031182000081919.
- 1053 **Reiss, T., Theis, H. I., Gonzalez-Delgado, A., Vega-Rodriguez, J., Zipfel, P. F., Skerka, C. and**
1054 **Pradel, G.** (2021). Acquisition of human plasminogen facilitates complement evasion by the
1055 malaria parasite *Plasmodium falciparum*. *European journal of immunology* **51**, 490–493. doi:
1056 10.1002/eji.202048718.
- 1057 **Ricklin, D., Hajishengallis, G., Yang, K. and Lambris, J. D.** (2010). Complement: a key system
1058 for immune surveillance and homeostasis. *Nature immunology* **11**, 785–797. doi:
1059 10.1038/ni.1923.
- 1060 **Rodríguez, D., Morrison, C. J. and Overall, C. M.** (2010). Matrix metalloproteinases: What do
1061 they not do? New substrates and biological roles identified by murine models and proteomics.
1062 *Matrix Metalloproteinases* **1803**, 39–54. doi: 10.1016/j.bbamcr.2009.09.015.

- 1063 **Rogove, A. D., Siao, C.-J., Keyt, B., Strickland, S. and Tsirka, S. E.** (1999). Activation of
1064 microglia reveals a non-proteolytic cytokine function for tissue plasminogen activator in the
1065 central nervous system. *Journal of Cell Science* **112**, 4007–4016. doi:
1066 10.1242/jcs.112.22.4007.
- 1067 **Saleem, S., Wang, D., Zhao, T., Sullivan, R. D. and Reed, G. L.** (2021). Matrix Metalloproteinase-
1068 9 Expression is Enhanced by Ischemia and Tissue Plasminogen Activator and Induces
1069 Hemorrhage, Disability and Mortality in Experimental Stroke. *Neuroscience* **460**, 120–129.
1070 doi: 10.1016/j.neuroscience.2021.01.003.
- 1071 **Saric, J., Li, J. V., Utzinger, J., Wang, Y., Keiser, J., Dirnhofer, S., Beckonert, O., Sharabiani,
1072 M. T. A., Fonville, J. M., Nicholson, J. K. and Holmes, E.** (2010). Systems parasitology:
1073 effects of *Fasciola hepatica* on the neurochemical profile in the rat brain. *Molecular systems
1074 biology* **6**, 396. doi: 10.1038/msb.2010.49.
- 1075 **Saunders, W. B., Bayless, K. J. and Davis, G. E.** (2005). MMP-1 activation by serine proteases
1076 and MMP-10 induces human capillary tubular network collapse and regression in 3D collagen
1077 matrices. *Journal of cell science* **118**, 2325–2340. doi: 10.1242/jcs.02360.
- 1078 **Serrat, J., Becerro-Recio, D., Torres-Valle, M., Simón, F., Valero, M. A., Bargues, M. D., Mas-
1079 Coma, S., Siles-Lucas, M. and González-Miguel, J.** (2023a). *Fasciola hepatica* juveniles
1080 interact with the host fibrinolytic system as a potential early-stage invasion mechanism. *PLoS
1081 neglected tropical diseases* **17**, e0010936. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0010936.
- 1082 **Serrat, J., Torres-Valle, M., López-García, M., Becerro-Recio, D., Siles-Lucas, M. and
1083 González-Miguel, J.** (2023b). Molecular Characterization of the Interplay between *Fasciola*
1084 *hepatica* Juveniles and Laminin as a Mechanism to Adhere to and Break through the Host
1085 Intestinal Wall. *International journal of molecular sciences* **24**,. doi: 10.3390/ijms24098165.

- 1086 **Serrat, J., Torres-Valle, M., De Marco Verissimo, C., Siles-Lucas, M. and González-Miguel, J.**
1087 (2025a). Binding and cleavage of pro-urokinase by a tegument extract of *Fasciola hepatica*
1088 newly excysted juveniles activate the host fibrinolytic system. *Veterinary research* **56**, 20.
1089 doi: 10.1186/s13567-025-01449-4.
- 1090 **Serrat, J., López-García, M., Torres-Valle, M., Molina-Hernández, V., Ruiz-Campillo, M. T.,**
1091 **Siles-Lucas, M. and González-Miguel, J.** (2025b). Early host–parasite interaction models
1092 reveal a key role for fibrinolysis in *Fasciola hepatica* intestinal migration. *Parasites & Vectors*
1093 **18**, 387. doi: 10.1186/s13071-025-06992-9.
- 1094 **Shi, Y., Toet, H., Rathinasamy, V., Young, N. D., Gasser, R. B., Beddoe, T., Huang, W. and**
1095 **Spithill, T. W.** (2014). First insight into CD59-like molecules of adult *Fasciola hepatica*.
1096 *Experimental parasitology* **144**, 57–64. doi: 10.1016/j.exppara.2014.06.012.
- 1097 **Shin, S. M., Cho, K. S., Choi, M. S., Lee, S. H., Han, S.-H., Kang, Y.-S., Kim, H. J., Cheong, J.**
1098 **H., Shin, C. Y. and Ko, K. H.** (2010). Urokinase-type plasminogen activator induces BV-2
1099 microglial cell migration through activation of matrix metalloproteinase-9. *Neurochemical*
1100 *research* **35**, 976–985. doi: 10.1007/s11064-010-0141-3.
- 1101 **Silva, L. S., Pinheiro, A. S., Teixeira, D. E., Silva-Aguiar, R. P., Peruchetti, D. B., Scharfstein,**
1102 **J., Caruso-Neves, C. and Pinheiro, A. A. S.** (2019a). Kinins Released by Erythrocytic
1103 Stages of *Plasmodium falciparum* Enhance Adhesion of Infected Erythrocytes to Endothelial
1104 Cells and Increase Blood Brain Barrier Permeability via Activation of Bradykinin Receptors.
1105 *Frontiers in medicine* **6**, 75. doi: 10.3389/fmed.2019.00075.
- 1106 **Silva, L. M., Lum, A. G., Tran, C., Shaw, M. W., Gao, Z., Flick, M. J., Moutsopoulos, N. M.,**
1107 **Bugge, T. H. and Mullins, E. S.** (2019b). Plasmin-mediated fibrinolysis enables macrophage
1108 migration in a murine model of inflammation. *Blood* **134**, 291–303. doi:
1109 10.1182/blood.2018874859.

- 1110 **Simon, D. I., Wei, Y., Zhang, L., Rao, N. K., Xu, H., Chen, Z., Liu, Q., Rosenberg, S. and**
1111 **Chapman, H. A.** (2000). Identification of a urokinase receptor-integrin interaction site.
1112 Promiscuous regulator of integrin function. *The Journal of biological chemistry* **275**, 10228–
1113 10234. doi: 10.1074/jbc.275.14.10228.
- 1114 **Smith, H. W. and Marshall, C. J.** (2010). Regulation of cell signalling by uPAR. *Nature reviews.*
1115 *Molecular cell biology* **11**, 23–36. doi: 10.1038/nrm2821.
- 1116 **Smout, M. J., Sotillo, J., Laha, T., Papatpremsiri, A., Rinaldi, G., Pimenta, R. N., Chan, L. Y.,**
1117 **Johnson, M. S., Turnbull, L., Whitchurch, C. B., Giacomini, P. R., Moran, C. S.,**
1118 **Golledge, J., Daly, N., Sripana, B., Mulvenna, J. P., Brindley, P. J. and Loukas, A.** (2015).
1119 Carcinogenic Parasite Secretes Growth Factor That Accelerates Wound Healing and
1120 Potentially Promotes Neoplasia. *PLoS pathogens* **11**, e1005209. doi:
1121 10.1371/journal.ppat.1005209.
- 1122 **Sonoki, A., Okano, Y. and Yoshitake, Y.** (2018). Dermal fibroblasts can activate matrix
1123 metalloproteinase-1 independent of keratinocytes via plasmin in a 3D collagen model.
1124 *Experimental dermatology* **27**, 520–525. doi: 10.1111/exd.13522.
- 1125 **Stack, M. S. and Pizzo, S. V.** (1993). Modulation of tissue plasminogen activator-catalyzed
1126 plasminogen activation by synthetic peptides derived from the amino-terminal heparin
1127 binding domain of fibronectin. *The Journal of biological chemistry* **268**, 18924–18928.
- 1128 **Stack, S., Gonzalez-Gronow, M. and Pizzo, S. V.** (1990). Regulation of plasminogen activation by
1129 components of the extracellular matrix. *Biochemistry* **29**, 4966–4970. doi:
1130 10.1021/bi00472a029.
- 1131 **Stack, S., Gray, R. D. and Pizzo, S. V.** (1991). Modulation of plasminogen activation and type IV
1132 collagenase activity by a synthetic peptide derived from the laminin A chain. *Biochemistry*
1133 **30**, 2073–2077. doi: 10.1021/bi00222a011.

- 1134 **Stepanova, V., Jayaraman, P.-S., Zaitsev, S. V., Lebedeva, T., Bdeir, K., Kershaw, R., Holman,**
1135 **K. R., Parfyonova, Y. V., Semina, E. V., Beloglazova, I. B., Tkachuk, V. A. and Cines,**
1136 **D. B.** (2016). Urokinase-type Plasminogen Activator (uPA) Promotes Angiogenesis by
1137 Attenuating Proline-rich Homeodomain Protein (PRH) Transcription Factor Activity and De-
1138 repressing Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF) Receptor Expression*. *Journal of*
1139 *Biological Chemistry* **291**, 15029–15045. doi: 10.1074/jbc.M115.678490.
- 1140 **Su, E. J., Fredriksson, L., Geyer, M., Folestad, E., Cale, J., Andrae, J., Gao, Y., Pietras, K.,**
1141 **Mann, K., Yepes, M., Strickland, D. K., Betsholtz, C., Eriksson, U. and Lawrence, D. A.**
1142 (2008). Activation of PDGF-CC by tissue plasminogen activator impairs blood-brain barrier
1143 integrity during ischemic stroke. *Nature medicine* **14**, 731–737. doi: 10.1038/nm1787.
- 1144 **Sugiki, M., Yoshida, E., Anai, K. and Maruyama, M.** (1998). Activation of single-chain
1145 urokinase-type plasminogen activator by a hemorrhagic metalloproteinase, jararafibrase I, in
1146 Bothrops jararaca venom. *Toxicon: official journal of the International Society on*
1147 *Toxinology* **36**, 993–1000. doi: 10.1016/s0041-0101(97)00137-2.
- 1148 **Suzuki, K., Enghild, J. J., Morodomi, T., Salvesen, G. and Nagase, H.** (1990). Mechanisms of
1149 activation of tissue procollagenase by matrix metalloproteinase 3 (stromelysin). *Biochemistry*
1150 **29**, 10261–10270. doi: 10.1021/bi00496a016.
- 1151 **Swisher, J. F. A., Khatri, U. and Feldman, G. M.** (2007). Annexin A2 is a soluble mediator of
1152 macrophage activation. *Journal of leukocyte biology* **82**, 1174–1184. doi:
1153 10.1189/jlb.0307154.
- 1154 **Tritten, L., Ballesteros, C., Beech, R., Geary, T. G. and Moreno, Y.** (2021). Mining nematode
1155 protein secretomes to explain lifestyle and host specificity. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases*
1156 **15**, e0009828. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0009828.

- 1157 **Tsunezumi, J., Yamamoto, K., Higashi, S. and Miyazaki, K.** (2008). Matrilysin (matrix
1158 metalloprotease-7) cleaves membrane-bound annexin II and enhances binding of tissue-type
1159 plasminogen activator to cancer cell surfaces. *The FEBS journal* **275**, 4810–4823. doi:
1160 10.1111/j.1742-4658.2008.06620.x.
- 1161 **Tu, W.-C. and Lai, S.-C.** (2006). *Angiostrongylus cantonensis*: efficacy of albendazole-
1162 dexamethasone co-therapy against infection-induced plasminogen activators and eosinophilic
1163 meningitis. *Experimental parasitology* **113**, 8–15. doi: 10.1016/j.exppara.2005.11.017.
- 1164 **Vago, J. P., Sugimoto, M. A., Lima, K. M., Negreiros-Lima, G. L., Baik, N., Teixeira, M. M.,**
1165 **Perretti, M., Parmer, R. J., Miles, L. A. and Sousa, L. P.** (2019). Plasminogen and the
1166 Plasminogen Receptor, Plg-R(KT), Regulate Macrophage Phenotypic, and Functional
1167 Changes. *Frontiers in immunology* **10**, 1458. doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2019.01458.
- 1168 **Waltz, D. A., Natkin, L. R., Fujita, R. M., Wei, Y. and Chapman, H. A.** (1997). Plasmin and
1169 plasminogen activator inhibitor type 1 promote cellular motility by regulating the interaction
1170 between the urokinase receptor and vitronectin. *The Journal of clinical investigation* **100**, 58–
1171 67. doi: 10.1172/JCI119521.
- 1172 **Wang, S., Ghosh, A. K., Bongio, N., Stebbings, K. A., Lampe, D. J. and Jacobs-Lorena, M.**
1173 (2012). Fighting malaria with engineered symbiotic bacteria from vector mosquitoes.
1174 *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **109**,
1175 12734–12739. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1204158109.
- 1176 **Weiß, E. and Kretschmer, D.** (2018). Formyl-Peptide Receptors in Infection, Inflammation, and
1177 Cancer. *Trends in immunology* **39**, 815–829. doi: 10.1016/j.it.2018.08.005.
- 1178 **Whyte, C. S.** (2023). All tangled up: interactions of the fibrinolytic and innate immune systems.
1179 *Frontiers in medicine* **10**, 1212201. doi: 10.3389/fmed.2023.1212201.

- 1180 **Williamson, A. L., Lustigman, S., Oksov, Y., Deumic, V., Plieskatt, J., Mendez, S., Zhan, B.,**
1181 **Bottazzi, M. E., Hotez, P. J. and Loukas, A.** (2006). Ancylostoma caninum MTP-1, an
1182 astacin-like metalloprotease secreted by infective hookworm larvae, is involved in tissue
1183 migration. *Infection and immunity* **74**, 961–967. doi: 10.1128/IAI.74.2.961-967.2006.
- 1184 **Xu, Z., Shi, H., Li, Q., Mei, Q., Bao, J., Shen, Y. and Xu, J.** (2008). Mouse macrophage
1185 metalloelastase generates angiostatin from plasminogen and suppresses tumor angiogenesis
1186 in murine colon cancer. *Oncology reports* **20**, 81–88.
- 1187 **Yang, J., Qiu, C., Xia, Y., Yao, L., Fu, Z., Yuan, C., Feng, X. and Lin, J.** (2010). Molecular
1188 cloning and functional characterization of Schistosoma japonicum enolase which is highly
1189 expressed at the schistosomulum stage. *Parasitology research* **107**, 667–677. doi:
1190 10.1007/s00436-010-1913-z.
- 1191 **Yang, Y., Bai, X., Li, C., Tong, M., Zhang, P., Cai, W., Liu, X. and Liu, M.** (2019). Molecular
1192 Characterization of Fructose-1,6-bisphosphate Aldolase From Trichinella spiralis and Its
1193 Potential in Inducing Immune Protection. *Frontiers in cellular and infection microbiology* **9**,
1194 122. doi: 10.3389/fcimb.2019.00122.
- 1195 **Yeh, Y.-T., Del Álamo, J. C. and Caffrey, C. R.** (2024). Biomechanics of parasite migration within
1196 hosts. *Trends in parasitology* **40**, 164–175. doi: 10.1016/j.pt.2023.12.001.
- 1197 **Yuan, H., Vance, K. M., Junge, C. E., Geballe, M. T., Snyder, J. P., Hepler, J. R., Yepes, M.,**
1198 **Low, C.-M. and Traynelis, S. F.** (2009). The serine protease plasmin cleaves the amino-
1199 terminal domain of the NR2A subunit to relieve zinc inhibition of the N-methyl-D-aspartate
1200 receptors. *The Journal of biological chemistry* **284**, 12862–12873. doi:
1201 10.1074/jbc.M805123200.
- 1202 **Zhang, Y., Zhou, Z.-H., Bugge, T. H. and Wahl, L. M.** (2007). Urokinase-type plasminogen
1203 activator stimulation of monocyte matrix metalloproteinase-1 production is mediated by

1204 plasmin-dependent signaling through annexin A2 and inhibited by inactive plasmin. *Journal*
1205 *of immunology (Baltimore, Md. : 1950)* **179**, 3297–3304. doi: 10.4049/jimmunol.179.5.3297.

1206 **Zhou, W., Li, X., Yang, X. and Ye, B.** (2024). The In Vitro Promoting Angiogenesis Roles of
1207 Exosomes Derived from the Protoscoleces of *Echinococcus multilocularis*. *Journal of*
1208 *microbiology and biotechnology* **34**, 1410–1418. doi: 10.4014/jmb.2403.03042.

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1210

1211 **Figure legends**

1212 **Figure 1. Overview of the fibrinolytic cascade. (1,2)** After vascular repair, dissolution of the blood
1213 clot starts by binding of the zymogen PLG to lysine residues of the fibrin within the clot, which
1214 exposes the cleavage site for proteases that function as PLG activators, namely the t-PA and the u-
1215 PA. **(3,4)** Upon cleavage, PLG is converted into its catalytically active form, the serine protease
1216 plasmin, which degrades fibrin. Fibrin degradation by plasmin stimulates blood clot dissolution and
1217 the restoration of normal blood flow. The activities of the PLG/plasmin system are regulated by
1218 different inhibitors, including PAI-1 and α 2-antiplasmin, which inhibit t-PA/u-PA and plasmin,
1219 respectively [3]. PAI-1, plasminogen activator inhibitor 1; PLG, plasminogen; t-PA, tissue-type
1220 plasminogen activator; u-PA, urokinase-type plasminogen activator. Created with Biorender.com.

1221

1222 **Figure 2. The pleiotropic effects of the PLG/plasmin system in inflammation.** The involvement
1223 of the PLG/plasmin system in inflammatory responses is mediated by the ability of different
1224 fibrinolytic components to regulate the complement cascade, fibrinolysis, chemotaxis, cell adhesion,
1225 cell migration, intracellular signalling, and the resolution of inflammation. **(1)** Plasmin cleaves
1226 different components of the complement system, including C3, C3b, and C5, which results in either
1227 activation or inhibition of the cascade. **(2)** Fibrin is deposited at sites of tissue damage, forming a
1228 scaffold for leukocyte recruitment through the engagement of integrin α _M β ₂. **(3)** Fibrin degradation
1229 by plasmin generates FDPs with chemotactic properties. Chemotaxis is also stimulated by plasmin
1230 cleavage of certain chemokines, which generates truncated versions that stimulate leukocyte
1231 recruitment. **(4)** The involvement of the PLG/plasmin system in the adhesion of inflammatory cells
1232 is mainly mediated by the u-PAR, which binds to the somatomedin B domain of vitronectin, a major
1233 component of the ECM. **(5)** Plasmin promotes cell migration by directly cleaving ECM proteins,
1234 including laminin and fibronectin, and by activating MMP zymogens into their active forms. The u-
1235 PA is also capable of cleaving and activating pro-MMPs irrespective of plasmin generation. **(6)**

1236 Intracellular signalling events that drive inflammatory responses are mainly regulated by FDPs and
1237 the u-PAR, which activate intracellular signalling receptors that modulate the production of pro- and
1238 anti-inflammatory cytokines. (7) The PLG/plasmin system participates in inflammation resolution
1239 by stimulating the polarisation of macrophages towards an anti-inflammatory or pro-resolution M2
1240 phenotype and by promoting apoptosis of leukocytes, fibrin clearance, and the stimulation of anti-
1241 inflammatory cytokine release. CCL21, C-C motif chemokine ligand 21; ECM, extracellular matrix;
1242 EGFR, epidermal growth factor receptor; FDP, fibrin degradation product; FPR1, formyl peptide
1243 receptor 1; GPCR, G protein-coupled receptor; MAPK, mitogen-activated protein kinase; MMP,
1244 matrix metalloprotease; PKC, protein kinase C; PLG, plasminogen; PLG-R, plasminogen receptor;
1245 pro-MMP, precursor of matrix metalloprotease; u-PA, urokinase-type plasminogen activator; u-PAR,
1246 receptor of the urokinase-type plasminogen activator. Created with Biorender.com.

1247

1248 **Figure 3. Relevant aspects of the interaction between parasites and the mammalian fibrinolytic**
1249 **system.** The most common mechanism of parasite-fibrinolysis interaction is through the expression
1250 of PLG-Rs that allow for PLG recruitment at the parasite surface (1) and subsequent plasmin
1251 generation (4) in the presence of host-derived PAs (6). Parasitic PLG-Rs are expressed on the parasite
1252 surface (1) or secreted externally, either freely (2) or within EVs (3) (Supp. File 2). (5,7) The
1253 interaction between PLG and parasitic receptors is lysine-dependent, as demonstrated in experiments
1254 including ϵ -ACA and CBXP during incubation with PLG, which inhibits the interaction [11,12]. (8)
1255 Parasitic PLG-Rs are often intracellular enzymes (such as α -enolase) with moonlighting potential.
1256 The mechanism of secretion or surface re-location of these proteins is not completely understood. (9)
1257 Parasitic PLG-Rs represent potential vaccine candidates for parasitic diseases [11]. (10,11) Enzymes
1258 capable of directly cleaving PLG have been identified in *S. mansoni* and *P. falciparum*. Enzymes that
1259 cleave the precursor of u-PA into its catalytically-active form have recently been described in *F.*
1260 *hepatica* juveniles [15] (not represented in this figure). (12) An overstimulation of the host
1261 fibrinolytic system by parasites can have pathogenic consequences; therefore, a balance must exist

1262 between the benefits gained by the parasite and the long-term negative effects that are generated in
1263 the host as a result of the interaction between parasites and the host fibrinolytic system [11]. ALF,
1264 angiotatin-like fragment; CBXP, carboxypeptidase; Eno, α -enolase; PA, plasminogen activator;
1265 PLG, plasminogen; PLG-R, plasminogen receptor; Plm, plasmin; t-PA, tissue-type plasminogen
1266 activator; u-PA, urokinase-type plasminogen activator; VAC, vaccine; ϵ -ACA, aminocaproic acid.
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